

Federated Learning for 6G Security: A Survey on Threats, Solutions and Research Directions

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Abstract—The Sixth-Generation (6G) are already in the horizon, owing to advents of communication technologies towards enabling intelligent applications and services. Federated Learning (FL) is a distributed Artificial Intelligence (AI) technology that underpins 6G communication technologies and applications. Interestingly, FL is also a promising contender to enhance 6G security. This paper presents a comprehensive and up-to-date review of FL-enabled 6G security. The paper explores security threats in FL for 6G, threats in FL for 6G, and threats shared across FL and 6G. Subsequently, how FL can be utilized to strengthen 6G security in the Radio Access Network (RAN), Open RAN (O-RAN), network edge, and network orchestration and core is presented. In addition, FL is for 6G application and service security across various emerging applications, ranging from Connected Autonomous Vehicles (CAVs) to the envisaged metaverse applications. The paper then consolidates lessons learned, projects, and proposes future research directions to establish the role of FL in strengthening 6G security.

Index Terms—6G, Network Security, Federated Learning, Distributed Learning

I. INTRODUCTION

The Sixth-Generation (6G) of mobile networks are expected to dawn by 2030 and is already advancing towards technical realisation, as outlined in the 3rd Generation Partnership Project (3GPP) Release 20 [1]. This release is dedicated to studies focusing on the 6G radio interface and core network architecture, with work commencing in June 2025. These developments are driven by advances in communication technologies, including the Internet of Everything (IoE), net-

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work intelligence, self-sustaining networks, Zero-touch Service Management (ZSM), and the convergence of Communications, Computing, Control, Localization, and Sensing [2]. These advanced capabilities will enable a wide range of futuristic applications and services, including the metaverse, Industry 5.0, Smart Grid 2.0, Collaborative Robots (Cobots), and Connected Autonomous Vehicles (CAVs) [3]. In line with these developments, the 6G standardization roadmap is designed to enable the first wave of commercial 6G system deployments in 2030 [4]. It is undeniable that one of the foundational technologies of 6G is Artificial Intelligence (AI) [5]. AI models, such as Machine Learning (ML) and Deep Learning (DL), are trained using large data sets, allowing the models to learn, self-teach, and evolve as intelligent entities. In contrast to centralized AI models, Federated Learning (FL) performs model computation locally at end nodes and devices, followed by sharing the local model parameters with edge or cloud servers for global model aggregation. The updated global model parameters are then distributed to end nodes and devices [6] [7]. This makes FL a scalable, decentralized, secure, privacy-preserving, and efficient AI solution for realizing 6G technologies, applications, and services [8].

One of the prominent applications of FL in future 6G networks is enhancing 6G security. With exponentially increasing cyberattacks, especially those leveraging AI capabilities [9], securing 6G networks that will connect critical infrastructures, including smart cities, industries, energy grids, healthcare, vehicular networks, and finance, is essential. This need is further reinforced by legal requirements for data security and privacy, such as the Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act (HIPAA)¹ in the USA and the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) in the European Union².

A. FL enabled 6G Security

The evolution of mobile networks toward 6G also expands the threat landscape in mobile networks [10]. The 6G threat landscape includes pre-5G and 5G security threats, as well as new security threats arising from the novel 6G network architecture, which extends to tiny cells, network meshes, and ZSM. Furthermore, the 6G threat landscape expands with the adoption of 6G technologies such as AI, ML, DL, FL, blockchain, Visible Light Communication (VLC), and quantum computing [11].

¹<https://www.cdc.gov/php/publications/topic/hipaa.html>

²<https://gdpr-info.eu/issues/data-protection-officer/>

Fig. 1: A summary of the structure, flow of information and outline of the paper highlighting FL for 6G security taxonomy.

While requiring special measures to address its own security challenges, AI is also expected to become a key technological enabler in addressing the security and privacy issues of 6G. For example, AI can address pre-5G threats by using intelligent, multi-layered intrusion detection and prevention systems based on DL technologies such as deep reinforcement learning and deep neural networks. As a result, threats from Distributed Denial of Service (DDoS) attacks, host location hijacking attacks, IP spoofing attacks, and anomaly-based intrusions can be detected and prevented much more efficiently than with conventional approaches [11]. However, given the distributed nature of 6G networks, AI-based technologies that handle critical tasks such as network security and privacy will primarily rely on edge intelligence, which offers lower delays and improved communication efficiency. In line with this, the 3GPP TR 23.700 series broadly investigates system and architectural support for AI/ML, including FL and distributed intelligence across edge-enabled networks, providing foundational insights toward beyond-5G and 6G systems [12]. Moreover, both the International Telecommunication Union - ITU-T Focus Group on Technologies for Network 2030 (FG-NET-2030) and the International Mobile Telecommunication's IMT-2030 framework for 6G define ubiquitous intelligence that is largely driven by distributed AI/ML techniques, such as FL, for future 6G networks [13]. This is further solidified by the Next G Alliance, prioritising FL as a critical enabler of preserving security and privacy of 6G and beyond networks [14].

Edge-based ML models, such as FL, process data locally to preserve user privacy. This makes FL a promising approach for achieving AI-based security and privacy in 6G networks and applications. For instance, FL offers intrusion detection at the network edge, which can minimize threats to 6G. Moreover, FL enables secure and privacy-preserving ZSM that can locally process sensitive data while facilitating network elements to improve ZSM jointly through collaborating securely [15]–[17]. Additionally, FL can enhance the security and privacy of 6G applications that range from Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) to metaverse/Augmented Reality (AR)/Virtual Reality

(VR) by minimising the data centralisation risk. However, despite the range of potential advantages, FL also has several vulnerabilities resulting in privacy concerns. FL also faces several challenges for a feasible adoption, as in the statistical dissimilarities with non-independent and Identically Distributed (non-IID) data across the FL domain, scalability limitations posed by communication loads in the convergence stage, heterogeneity among the FL nodes, and security issues presented with arbitrarily adversarial device behaviors along with poisoning threats [18]. Consequently, integrating FL to 6G also opens up a new security and privacy vulnerabilities. Hence, it is evident that there is a eminent demand for a comprehensive study on how to utilize FL for 6G security and privacy while addressing any security vulnerabilities of FL, towards strengthening security in emerging 6G networks.

B. Motivation and Contributions

Realizing the potential of FL to strengthen 6G security, several research works have explored FL-related security and privacy challenges. A vision of 6G security and key performance indicators is presented in [10], which also explores the threat landscape in 6G network architecture. This presents a general overview of B5G security, without focusing on FL. FL applications for envisioned sixth generation 6G wireless networks are explored in [8], whereas the conceptual techniques, software platforms and challenges of FL in 6G are presented in [19]. Vulnerabilities and defences for FL and FL for application security is discussed in [20]. [21] reviews distributed ML architectures and designs on communication optimisation, resource distribution, privacy and security in B5G. Fundamentals and enabling technologies of FL in wireless networks edge is explored in [22] while distributed edge learning techniques in advanced communication optimization designs is elaborated in [23]. In addition, FL vulnerabilities, attacks, and the usage of FL to enhance 5G and 6G is presented in [24]. A summary of important surveys on FL enabled B5G and 6G security is portrayed in Table I.

TABLE I: Summary of Important Surveys on FL enabled 6G Security

Ref.	Contribution	FL in 6G	FL Threats for 6G	FL for 6G Security	FL for 6G Application Security
[8]	FL applications for envisioned sixth generation 6G wireless networks	Yes	No	No	No
[10]	6G security and privacy key performance indicators and the threat landscape in 6G network architecture	No	No	Partially	No
[20]	FL vulnerabilities, defences for FL vulnerabilities, FL for application security	Yes	No	Partially	Yes
[19]	Conceptual techniques, software platforms and challenges of FL in 6G	Yes	No	Partially	No
[21]	Review distributed ML architectures and designs on communication optimisation, resource distribution, privacy and security in B5G	Yes	No	Partial	No
[22]	Fundamentals and enabling technologies of FL in wireless networks edge	Yes	No	No	No
[23]	Distributed edge learning techniques in advanced communication optimization designs	Yes	No	Partial	No
[24]	Distributed edge learning techniques in advanced communication optimization designs	Partial	Partial	Partial	No
This Survey	A comprehensive survey on FL enabled 6G security	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes

No No information or explores the area briefly

Partial Provides some information about the area

Yes Explores the area in detail

However, none of the existing studies offers a comprehensive and in-depth discussion specific to FL enabled 6G Security by extensively exploring aspects ranging from FL enabled 6G, security threats raised with the integration of FL to 6G, ranging from security threats in FL for 6G, security threats in 6G for FL, to shared threats across FL and 6G. Furthermore, FL enabled 6G security in IoT, RAN, Edge, Network Core and ZSM. Moreover, FL in 6G application security in a broad spectrum of applications, ranging from Connected Autonomous Vehicles (CAV), Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAV), healthcare, Industry 5.0, and metaverse/AR/VR and FL security issues have not been comprehensively explored comprehensively in the literature. This highlights a significant void for a comprehensive and up-to-date literature survey on FL for 6G security towards facilitating research, standardization and technology development of FL enabled security in the 6G era, which is addressed by this paper as portrayed in Table I. This paper focuses on providing a comprehensive and up-to-date review of FL for 6G security. The main contributions of this review are as follows.

- Explore new security issues raised in deploying FL in 6G networks, ranging from security threats in FL for 6G, and 6G threats for FL, to shared threats across FL and 6G.
- Evaluate the role of FL for 6G security ranging from 6G device and IoT security, RAN/Open RAN (O-RAN) security, edge network security, orchestration and core network security including ZSM and cloud native security.
- Assess how FL can strengthen 6G application security, ranging from various emerging applications including, CAV and UAV, healthcare, Industry 5.0, and metaverse/AR/VR and other applications.
- Present lessons learned, ongoing projects and propose promising future research directions towards FL enabled 6G security.

C. Outline

The rest of the review is organized as illustrated in Fig. 1, which provides a summary of the structure, flow of information and outline of the paper, while highlighting a FL for 6G security taxonomy. Section II provides a in-depth overview of the concept of FL along with envisaged developments of 6G. The role of FL in 6G networks is discussed in Section III. Security threats for FL-enabled 6G are explored in Section IV. Subsequently, how FL can strengthen 6G security is presented in Section V. Section VI elaborates how FL strengthens 6G application security. The lessons learned, projects and future research directions are presented in Section VII while Section VIII concludes the paper.

II. BACKGROUND

This section introduces FL as a concept, with reference to 6G developments. Subsequently, an overview of the developments in communication technologies towards 6G are presented.

A. Federated Learning

1) *Introduction:* FL enables devices (e.g., smartphones, sensors, base stations) to collaboratively train shared models without transferring their raw data to a central server [25]. Instead, only model updates (e.g., gradients or weights) are communicated, significantly enhancing privacy and reducing bandwidth usage. Table II, compares centralized learning, distributed learning and FL, across aspects, such as, data location, model training, communication cost, and scalability to identify that FL is ideal for 6G considering various aspects, including, latency, privacy, and network architecture.

2) *Methods/Taxonomy/Systems:* FL can be categorized according to two principal taxonomies: (i) network topology and (ii) data partitioning schemes [26], [27].

TABLE II: Comparison of Centralized, Distributed, and Federated Learning Paradigms

Aspect	Centralized Learning	Distributed Learning	Federated Learning
Data Location	All data is sent to a central server for training.	Data is partitioned and sent to worker nodes; still accessible centrally.	Data remains on local devices; only model updates are shared.
Model Training	Performed centrally on collected data.	Performed on distributed nodes; central aggregation.	Performed locally on each client, server aggregates model updates.
Privacy	Low – raw data is centralized.	Moderate – data is partitioned but still shared.	High – no raw data is transferred.
Communication Cost	High – all raw data must be uploaded.	Medium – depends on task/data size.	Low – only model updates are shared.
Scalability	Poor – central server becomes a bottleneck.	Good – load is shared across nodes.	Excellent – fully distributed architecture.
Suitability for 6G	Limited – privacy and latency issues.	Useful for edge AI tasks with some privacy compromises.	Ideal – aligns with privacy, latency, and the distributed nature of 6G.

TABLE III: Summary of FL Architectures and their applications in 6G.

FL Architecture	Description	Applications in 6G Networks
Centralized FL	Multiple clients independently train a model, and a central server aggregates their model parameters using weighted averaging to create and distribute an aggregated global model.	Improves data security and privacy. Enables efficient distributed learning across heterogeneous devices while optimizing resource distribution and managing network traffic.
Hierarchical FL	Clients send local models to edge servers for sub-global aggregation, which are then aggregated by cloud servers to create the final global model, enabling large-scale deployment, improved model performance, and enhanced data privacy.	Reduces communication latency. Clusters users around edge servers for efficient communication. Accelerates FL training and reduces communication overhead. Achieves higher model accuracy in non-IID settings.
Decentralized FL	Operates without a central server, using a peer-to-peer (P2P) network where clients perform local training and aggregate model updates directly from their neighbors, making it suitable for highly scalable network topologies.	Facilitates collaborative model training in the absence of a central server. Supports V2X networks for distributed training. Can be coupled with blockchain for secure model update exchanges.
Semi-Decentralized FL (semi-DFL)	Combines hierarchical and decentralized FL by organizing clients into clusters with edge servers for sub-aggregation, edge servers collaboratively compute the global model in a decentralized manner - suitable for large-scale networks, reduces communication burden and mitigates single points of failure.	Enhances scalability and reduces latency by processing data at the edge. Efficient for handling vast data generated by edge devices in 6G. Minimizes the need for central server coordination.

a) *Network Topology-Based FL Architectures*: FL architectures can be broadly categorized into Centralized FL (CFL), Hierarchical FL (HFL), Decentralized FL (DFL), and Semi-Decentralized FL (semi-DFL) [6]. Each architecture introduces distinct communication patterns between clients and aggregators and has different applications in 6G, as clearly presented in Table III. In CFL, a central server aggregates model updates received from all clients using schemes [28]. This approach is simple and widely adopted but suffers from a single point of failure [29]. HFL addresses this by introducing a multi-tier hierarchy, where edge servers first aggregate client updates before sending them to the cloud for final aggregation [30]–[32]. This reduces communication latency and scales well for non-IID settings [33]. DFL, in contrast, completely eliminates the need for a central server. Clients exchange model updates in a peer-to-peer manner to collaboratively train the global model [34], [35]. This is especially useful in infrastructure-less or highly mobile 6G environments, such as vehicle-to-everything (V2X) networks [36], [37]. DFL can also be integrated with blockchain to enhance trust and auditability [38]. Semi-DFL combines the robustness of DFL with the structured efficiency of HFL. It organizes clients into clusters managed by edge servers that perform sub-aggregations before engaging in inter-edge collaboration to compute the global model [39], [40]. This architecture is particularly suited for large-scale, latency-sensitive applications in 6G, where both scalability and resilience are critical.

b) *Data Partitioning-Based FL Paradigms*: FL can also be categorized based on how training data is distributed across clients, either by samples or features. The three major types are Horizontal FL (HoFL), Vertical FL (VFL), and Federated Transfer Learning (FTL) [5]. In HoFL, clients share the same feature space but differ in the samples they possess [41]. This allows all clients to train the same model structure locally,

with model updates aggregated by the server while preserving data privacy. In the context of 6G-enabled smart cities, where numerous IoT devices observe similar types of data but from different spatial contexts, HoFL enables collaborative training of global models while maintaining data locality [42]. VFL applies when clients hold different feature sets for the same set of users or samples [43], [44]. After securely aligning entities (i.e., entity alignment), encrypted local features from each client are used to collaboratively train a model [45]. This paradigm is highly relevant for Intelligent Transportation Systems (ITS) in 6G smart cities, where vehicle manufacturers, telecom operators, and road infrastructure authorities hold complementary datasets about the same vehicles or users [46], [47]. FTL is suitable when clients differ in both feature and sample space. It allows participants with limited data overlap to collaboratively learn via feature transformation and knowledge transfer [48]. FTL can benefit large-scale, heterogeneous 6G environments such as integrated terrestrial-satellite networks. For instance, edge nodes, mobile devices, and satellites can share minimal overlapping samples but still participate in model training via transfer learning [49], [50]. FTL has also proven effective in intrusion detection for 6G IoT [51].

3) *Emerging Trends in Federated Learning*: Beyond conventional FL architectures and data partitioning schemes, recent research is exploring innovative FL paradigms tailored to next-generation communication systems. This includes extending FL to support multimodal data fusion across heterogeneous devices, enabling distributed training of large language models at the network edge, and integrating mechanisms for selective forgetting through federated unlearning (FUL). These emerging trends are reshaping how intelligence is distributed across 6G networks while addressing critical challenges related to scalability, model personalization, data diversity, and

compliance with dynamic privacy regulations.

(i) *Multimodal Federated Learning (MFL)*: Single-modality data is increasingly inadequate for supporting the breadth and complexity of modern AI-driven applications. The rapid proliferation of IoT sensors, the advent of 6G networks, and advancements in edge and multimedia hardware have made it commonplace to collect heterogeneous data types such as images, audio, video, textual content, and geospatial measurements, all pertaining to the same task or environment. Leveraging such diverse sources can significantly enhance machine learning models' ability to infer, reason, and adapt in dynamic, context-rich settings. The core objective of multimodal learning lies in the fusion of these disparate modalities to produce richer, more context-aware models that outperform unimodal systems in tasks requiring holistic understanding, such as, autonomous navigation, personalized healthcare, smart surveillance, and immersive AR/VR environments. Multimodal datasets collected from user devices often contain highly sensitive information, including personal identifiers, proprietary business insights, or even national security-related content. Centralizing such data not only increases the risk of privacy breaches but also imposes significant burdens on storage infrastructure and network bandwidth, especially when scaled across global 6G-enabled ecosystems.

FL presents a natural solution to these issues by enabling collaborative model training across decentralized clients, without requiring raw data to leave its source. This paradigm is particularly well-aligned with 6G design principles, such as edge intelligence, ultra-low latency, and trust-by-design. As a result, the convergence of FL and multimodal learning, referred to as Multimodal Federated Learning (MFL), has become an emerging research frontier. MFL aims to combine the strengths of multimodal data fusion with the privacy-preserving, distributed architecture of FL. Current efforts in this direction are investigating architectural frameworks, fusion strategies, modality alignment, and optimization techniques to enable scalable, robust, and privacy-aware multimodal learning across decentralized environments [52], [53]. In this context, current literature recognises three modes of federation settings for multimodal data:

- *Single-Single (S-S)*: Each client owns a single modality and trains a unimodal local model, and the clients use the data of this modality to train the model and perform model aggregation through the server (Fig. 2).
- *Single-Multiple (S-M)*: In this mode, some clients have data in multiple modalities, and some clients have data in only one modality. In particular, clients learn the feature representation of a single modality or the feature representation of multiple modalities and realize the information interaction between the same modality or different modalities under different clients through the server aggregation model (Fig. 3).
- *Multiple-Multiple (M-M)*: Every client possesses several modalities and jointly optimizes a local multimodal model that is later merged globally to realize the information interaction of multimodal data under different clients (Fig. 4).

Fig. 2: The data on the client side is single-single modality

Fig. 3: The data on the client side is single-multiple modality

Fig. 4: The data on the client side is multiple modalities

MFL is particularly crucial for 6G applications such as federated healthcare analytics, collaborative autonomous systems, smart city surveillance, and cross-device virtual assistants. In particular, MFL-based solutions have shown improved model performance compared to their unimodal counterparts across several healthcare domains, including cardiovascular disease, sleep disorders detection, COVID-19 detection, and human activity recognition [54] [55].

(ii) *Federated Large Language Models (FLLMs)*: The emergence of Large Language Models (LLMs) such as GPT, BERT and LLaMA has significantly advanced natural language processing (NLP) in various applications. However, their enormous size and dependence on centralized data pose challenges for privacy, communication and energy efficiency, problems that are particularly pronounced in distributed 6G networks. Federated Large Language Models (FLLMs) offer a

promising solution as they allow LLMs to be trained collaboratively across edge nodes or client devices without transmitting raw data to a centralized server. This distributed training approach is well aligned with the 6G principles of Edge Intelligence, Data Sovereignty and Green Computing. Recent work in FLLMs explores architectural decompositions, such as federated fine-tuning of pre-trained LLMs and split learning over device-edge cloud hierarchies [56], [57]. For example, edge devices can tune small LLM adapters locally to domain-specific data while updating only low-rank or attention-specific parameters. This reduces communication overhead and preserves user privacy. In addition, privacy preserving mechanisms such as secure aggregation and differential privacy can be embedded to prevent leaks from model updates [56]. In the 6G era, FLLMs are expected to enable privacy-aware and context-aware conversational agents, on-device language understanding for AR/VR and multilingual services across global networks, all without relying on centralization of data.

FUL: FUL is an emerging paradigm that aims to remove the influence of specific clients or data samples from a jointly trained FL model [58]. This capability is critical for 6G networks that need to comply with strict data privacy regulations, such as the "right to be forgotten" under GDPR or similar data deletion requests in dynamic environments [59]. Unlike FL, which may require retraining from scratch to address these issues, FUL provides a more efficient pathway by allowing models to adapt incrementally. It is particularly relevant for long-term FL deployments in 6G infrastructures where client participation is volatile, data is often outdated, and privacy regulations are evolving. In particular, FUL not only helps maintain the model's accuracy and relevance in the face of non-stationary data but also enhances privacy and security by allowing for the dynamic adjustment of the model to exclude potentially compromised data and correct for injected vulnerabilities without communicating the raw data. As shown in Fig. 5, techniques such as knowledge distillation, influence functions, and approximate gradient removal are currently being developed to support unlearning in FL environments [60]. For example, in graph-based FUL, the system identifies and subtracts the impact of a client's updates across federated rounds by using local graph embeddings or perturbation-based methods. FUL also plays a crucial role in mitigating poisoning attacks by allowing untrustworthy or malicious data contributions to be revoked post hoc. In the context of 6G, FUL enables more robust and regulation-compliant AI by ensuring that federated models remain updatable, accountable, and reversible as the data landscape changes.

(iii) *Quantum Federated Learning (QFL):* QFL is a rapidly evolving interdisciplinary field at the intersection of Quantum Computing (QC) and FL. Its main objective is to leverage quantum mechanical principles to enhance privacy, security, computational efficiency, and scalability in distributed learning systems [61]. By combining the computational advantages of QC with the decentralized and privacy-preserving features of FL, QFL introduces a transformative paradigm that can significantly impact sectors such as healthcare, telecommunications, networking, smart cities, and intelligent transportation.

QFL offers several compelling benefits [62]. First, it en-

Fig. 5: Overview of the FUL workflow: The server or client initiates target removal during or after FL training, and the unlearner eliminates the target's contribution. The requesting client verifies the removal using evaluation metrics, resulting in the final unlearned model.

hances privacy and security through quantum-resilient mechanisms, such as quantum key distribution (QKD), which provide stronger protection against eavesdropping and adversarial attacks than classical cryptographic schemes. Second, QFL can accelerate the federated optimization process by leveraging quantum parallelism, superposition, and entanglement to enable faster gradient computations and model aggregation, which is particularly advantageous in latency-sensitive applications. Moreover, quantum data encoding and quantum amplitude compression techniques can substantially reduce communication overhead by allowing clients to transmit highly compressed model updates without compromising information fidelity. In addition, quantum-enabled optimizers can explore high-dimensional parameter spaces more efficiently, providing improved convergence rates and enhanced generalization capabilities in heterogeneous federated environments. Overall, QFL aims to harness the scalable computational capacity of quantum processors to collaboratively train complex models across numerous distributed nodes, ultimately paving the way for more secure, efficient, and scalable federated intelligence.

B. 6G Networks

1) *Distinction Between 5G and 6G:* 6G networks consist of heterogeneous IoT nodes that are integrated into various application scenarios in the industrial vertical. The computational capabilities of IoT nodes, mobile devices, sensors and actuators differ in production-grade 6G networks. Beyond 5G, the key distinguishing advancement of the 6G is the AI-native behavior in different layers of the network operations, including network slicing [63], [64], resource management [65], and security [11]. While both 5G and 6G use AI and edge computing to improve network intelligence, 6G introduces several unprecedented features that significantly increase the importance of federated learning. In contrast to 5G, which focuses on improved mobile broadband and low-latency communication, 6G envisions deeply integrated AI-native architectures, massive use of intelligent surfaces, sub-millisecond latency, ultra-high reliability and support for novel use cases such as real-time holographic communication, tactile internet, digital twins and multi-sensory XR environments. These capabilities require distributed intelligence at the network edge and

strict privacy preservation, conditions under which traditional centralized learning is not feasible. FL becomes essential in 6G to enable collaborative model training in highly heterogeneous, privacy-sensitive and resource-constrained environments, such as in smart vehicles, remote surgery with haptic feedback or massive IoT deployments, while being consistent with the zero-trust and self-sovereign identity principles expected in future 6G systems.

2) *Key Technologies Driving 6G Development:* The development of 6G is being driven by a number of cutting-edge technologies that go beyond the capabilities of 5G. One of the most anticipated technologies is terahertz (THz) communication, which operates in the 0.1–10 THz frequency range and promises ultra-high bandwidth and data rates in the terabits-per-second range. While THz communication opens up new use cases such as real-time holographic communication and the tactile Internet, it also brings new vulnerabilities such as susceptibility to interference and eavesdropping, which require advanced signal processing and secure communication protocols.

Another important technology is reconfigurable intelligent surfaces (RIS), which can dynamically change the wireless propagation environment by adjusting electromagnetic wave reflections. RIS improves spectral efficiency and enables fine-grained control of security at the physical layer, making it an ideal partner for privacy-aware network technologies such as FL. Integrated Sensing and Communications (ISAC) is another milestone in 6G technology. It combines communication with radar-like sensing to enable environmental awareness, localization and mapping. This convergence brings new challenges in terms of privacy and integrity, especially in location-sensitive applications where FL can support secure, collaborative model training without exposing raw data. A key feature of 6G is its AI-native architecture, where AI and ML are embedded directly into the network fabric. Unlike 5G, where AI is mainly used for optimization, 6G networks will configure, adapt and optimize themselves in real time. Federated learning plays a fundamental role in this distributed AI model, as it enables edge devices and network components to learn together from local data while preserving user privacy and reducing latency. Space-air-ground integrated networks are also central to the 6G vision. They aim to provide global connectivity through the seamless integration of terrestrial infrastructure with aerial (e.g., UAVs) and satellite communications. This multi-layered architecture extends connectivity but also creates complex issues around privacy and trust. FL helps mitigate these issues by enabling secure cross-domain learning without data centralization.

Finally, the anticipated rise of quantum computing brings both challenges and opportunities. While quantum technologies threaten current cryptographic methods, 6G networks are expected to incorporate quantum communication techniques such as QKD to improve security. FL systems, especially those integrated with post-quantum cryptography or quantum-inspired optimization, are being actively researched to protect 6G against evolving cyber threats.

TABLE IV: FL in 6G Layers

6G Layer	Role of FL in 6G Layers
Smart Application Layer	This layer uses FL-enabled distributed AI to facilitate intelligent 6G applications and services.
Network-centric Application Layer	FL-based network-centric applications facilitate intelligent system deployment, API management, and application-specific resource monitoring and management.
Intelligent Control Layer	This layer utilizes FL to control, monitor and manage intelligent networks.
Intelligent Edge Layer	This layer aggregates local models to perform global aggregation. In addition, local models can be shared among nodes.

III. ROLE OF FL IN 6G NETWORKS

Due to the inherently distributed nature of 6G, FL plays a prominent role in its AI-native architecture. FL operations involve local model training and sharing of model updates across the network toward cloud servers for global aggregation, enhancing AI-driven services. To ensure the scalability of 6G, computationally intensive processes such as model aggregation are offloaded to the edge layer, as shown in Figure 6. This vision architecture comprises of AI-enabling functions from Hexa-X-II 6G [66] applied at 6G layered architecture [67] where each layer presents the FL-enabling components. Here, 6G-based distributed AI applications are accessed at the smart application layer through AI-as-a-Service (AIaaS), where service providers and third-party organizations interact via a developer portal offering intent-based APIs. The network-centric application layer provides AI lifecycle management, supporting MLOps, closed-loop automation, and secure orchestration. The intelligent control layer manages execution, intrusion detection, and access control, while the intelligent edge layer performs local model aggregation with energy-efficient function allocation. The sensing layer, consisting of diverse connected devices, generates the training data used in FL workflows.

However, despite the benefits and shared responsibility, each of these layers introduces potential security threats. In the sensing layer, malicious clients [68] can inject poisoned updates, while passive eavesdropping devices [69] may compromise data confidentiality. Weak authentication mechanisms [70], [71], combined with resource-limited IoT nodes, reduce the feasibility of strong encryption. At the edge, attackers may attempt to infer client data or reconstruct original training inputs, degrading the accuracy of both local and global models. Server-side risks include compromised cloud aggregators and insider threats in the intelligent control layer, which can manipulate the global model. At the application layer, insufficient privacy standards and lack of transparency hinder user trust. Human-understandable AI explanations and governance mechanisms are essential for enabling secure AI-human collaboration. Therefore, the distributed, AI-native, and heterogeneous nature of 6G systems necessitates strong, multi-layered security for FL to deliver trustworthy and resilient services in next-generation networks.

1) *Key Benefits of FL for 6G:* Due to the multitude of advantages of FL and the inherently distributed nature of 6G networks, FL plays a significant role in 6G networks [72]. The role of FL in 6G vision is illustrated in Figure 6 and the role of FL in 6G layers is presented in Table IV. At the top,

Fig. 6: Role of FL in 6G vision architecture

the Smart Application Layer leverages ML to enhance various domains such as organizational operations, industrial automation, healthcare, and transport logistics. Then, the Network-centric Application Layer acts as a bridge, managing regulatory requirements, communication interfaces, and system deployments while ensuring application-specific Quality of Service (QoS). The Intelligent Control Layer oversees network functions, control, scheduling, monitoring, and secure access management. On the other hand, the Intelligent Edge Layer focuses on hierarchical aggregation of data and model sharing, facilitating cross-silo FL to enhance ML models without compromising data privacy. At the base, the Sensing Layer and Radio Access Network (RAN) support connectivity and data collection through fog nodes, cell site connections, and various devices such as mobile phones, smart vehicles, robots, and IoT devices. The Near-Real-Time RAN Intelligent Controller (Near-RT RIC), Radio Units (RU), Distributed Units (DU), and Centralized Units (CU) work together to manage and optimize the network performance in real-time. This layered architecture demonstrates how FL can enhance 6G layers while maintaining data privacy and regulatory compliance, contributing to the efficiency and effectiveness of the 6G network. Furthermore, compared to centralized learning, using FL for model training has several key advantages in 6G [29], including privacy, low latency, reduction of communication overhead, and scalability.

(i) *Privacy*: One of the key advantages of FL lies in its inherent privacy-preserving nature. FL significantly mitigates privacy concerns by keeping raw data where it is generated. This is because the data never leaves the user's device, substantially reducing the risk of privacy breaches and unauthorized data access. This becomes particularly critical in the context of 6G

networks as the volume of data generated by connected devices increases exponentially. FL enables secure data processing and model training directly at the edge, maintaining user privacy while leveraging the vast amounts of data produced in these advanced network environments. According to research, FL's decentralized approach is particularly beneficial in maintaining data privacy in scenarios involving sensitive information such as mobile traffic [73] [74].

(ii) *Low latency*: Sending raw data to a central server is time-consuming, making FL an ideal solution for ultra-low latency applications. FL enables wireless devices to learn a shared prediction model collaboratively and in parallel while keeping all training data on the device, significantly reducing data transmission times [75]. In an FL setting, the models can be continuously trained and updated, ensuring that the models remain relevant and accurate over time. Moreover, within the Multi-access Edge Computing (MEC) framework, instantaneous decisions, such as event detection, can be made at the local edge nodes or end devices. This local processing capability substantially reduces latency compared to a cloud-based model where decisions are made remotely before being transmitted back to the end devices. This setup is particularly beneficial for applications that require real-time responses, such as autonomous vehicles, augmented reality, and industrial automation. By processing data on edge, FL ensures that critical decisions can be made quickly, facilitating latency-sensitive applications [76]. The ability FL to support low latency is crucial for the success of 6G networks, which demand rapid data processing to meet the stringent performance requirements of next-generation applications. This decentralized approach accelerates decision-making processes and improves the overall user experience by minimizing delays.

(iii) *Scalability*: FL inherently offers an enhanced level of scalability. It helps to train ML models anywhere at any scale. This capability is crucial for handling the large volumes of data generated by numerous devices, promoting the scalability and accessibility of ML models. Firstly, FL allows for decentralized processing, distributing the computational load across multiple devices or nodes in the network. This results in a system that can easily scale with the increasing number of participating devices, each contributing to model training with their local datasets. The decentralized approach ensures that as more devices join the network, the system can leverage its computational resources to enhance model training efficiency [73]. Secondly, the distributed nature of FL aids in managing data heterogeneity and geographic distribution. Regardless of where data is generated or what it represents, every participating node in the network can contribute to the learning process. This makes the model more comprehensive and representative of diverse data sources. The ability to incorporate data from various locations and contexts ensures that the resulting models are robust and applicable to a wide range of scenarios [5]. Lastly, FL can efficiently handle scenarios where data cannot be moved due to legal, privacy, or logistical constraints. By bringing the model to the data, FL enables ML in previously inaccessible environments, significantly broadening the scale of potential applications. This approach respects data privacy and sovereignty and reduces the need for costly

data transfers, making it feasible to implement ML within terrestrial and non-terrestrial networks [77]. Therefore, FL's scalability is a key factor in its suitability for 6G networks, where the number of connected devices and the volume of data are expected to grow exponentially. By leveraging the distributed computational power of edge devices, FL facilitates the development of scalable, efficient, and privacy-preserving ML applications.

(iv) *Communication-Efficient FL*: FL significantly enhances communication efficiency by requiring the upload of model parameters to a centralized location instead of raw data. This approach drastically reduces the volume of information that needs to be transferred to the cloud, thus lowering the costs associated with data communication and alleviating the burden on network bandwidth [78]. In traditional centralized learning, raw data must be transmitted to a central server for processing and model training. This process can be highly inefficient, especially in networks with limited bandwidth or in scenarios where data is continuously generated at high rates. FL addresses this issue by keeping the raw data on local devices and only sharing the necessary model updates. These updates are typically much smaller than the raw data, leading to significant reductions in data transmission requirements [79]. Furthermore, FL's communication efficiency is particularly beneficial in resource-constrained environments like IoT devices and edge computing scenarios. By minimizing the amount of data that needs to be sent over the network, FL helps preserve the battery life of devices and reduces the overall energy consumption associated with data transfers. This efficiency also enables the deployment of the models in remote or rural areas where network infrastructure may be limited or expensive. Overall, the communication efficiency of FL not only enhances the feasibility of deploying ML in diverse and widespread network environments and contributes to more sustainable and cost-effective AI applications.

2) *Key challenges in FL for 6G*: Although FL offers a promising approach to improve privacy protection in 6G networks, its implementation in real-world applications presents several significant challenges [18]. These challenges encompass security and privacy concerns, systems, statistical heterogeneity, and concept drift, as highlighted in Table V.

(i) *Security and Privacy Concerns*: The successful deployment of FL for 6G networks necessitates robust security measures to counter various threats, including poisoning attacks, inference attacks, backdoor attacks, and communication bottlenecks [80] [81]. These threats can arise from multiple sources, such as data manipulation, aggregation algorithms, and communication protocols [82]. Attacks in FL are generally classified as data-based or model-based, as shown in Fig. 7. This figure divides security threats in FL into two main categories: poisoning and reverse engineering. Poisoning attacks aim to degrade the model's performance or inject specific malicious behaviors (backdoors) and are carried out through model-based methods (e.g., backdoor attacks) or data-based methods (e.g., data injection). Reverse engineering attacks seek to extract sensitive information, such as training data or proprietary model details, and are also classified as model-based (e.g., model inversion) or data-based (e.g., membership

Fig. 7: Novel attacks in FL for 6G categorized according to data-based and model-based in general.

inference). These threats are especially critical in 6G environments, where FL is widely deployed on resource-constrained and heterogeneous edge devices.

Attacks in FL can be executed by tampering with local data on end devices or by altering model parameters on the client or server side. Data-based attacks involve manipulating the data used to train the model on local devices. These attacks can be executed in several ways, such as poisoning attacks and label flipping, whereas model-based attacks focus on manipulating the model parameters during training or after the model updates, backdoor attacks and model poisoning.

For instance, an attacker could compromise an IoT device or network to manipulate local data or ML tasks, resulting in a poisoned model. Alternatively, an attacker might perform a man-in-the-middle attack to alter model updates during transmission or eavesdrop on communications, thus compromising user privacy [83]. An example of a model poisoning attack involves a malicious agent that causes the FL model to misclassify inputs selected with high confidence [84]. Several security solutions have been proposed to address these challenges in 6G networks. For example, a novel framework has been introduced to automatically detect malicious participants in the FL process using deep reinforcement learning to select a trusted network slice based on its reputation dynamically. This trusted participant is responsible for identifying poisoned model updates using unsupervised ML techniques [85]. Researchers have proposed defence approaches such as norm clipping and differential privacy to address backdoor attacks. Norm-clipping combats boosted attacks by placing a bound on the sensitivity of gradient updates, ignoring updates if their norm exceeds a certain threshold. Differential privacy supplements this by adding Gaussian noise to the updates, mitigating the effects of adversaries beyond what norm clipping can achieve [86]. DFL is another promising solution for securing the FL training process and addressing mistrust issues associated with centralized parameter servers. However, DFL can be vulnerable to attacks as the number of participants grows. For example, Sybil attacks can occur where malicious actors create multiple fake identities to influence model training [87] [88]. Blockchain technology has been integrated into FL settings to enhance the security of FL-based solutions further. Blockchain helps manage user reputations and decentralizes the learning process, eliminating the need for a single central server in model aggregation [89] [90]. Specifically, incorporating blockchain ensures that all transactions

TABLE V: Key Challenges in Federated Learning for 6G Networks

Challenge	Description	6G-Specific Solutions
Security and Privacy Concerns	Poisoning attacks, inference attacks, backdoor attacks, and communication bottlenecks [80], [81]. Data- or model-based attacks with data manipulation or altering model parameters [82]. e.g., Manipulation of IoT devices, man-in-the-middle attacks [83].	Deep reinforcement learning for detecting malicious participants [85]. Norm clipping and differential privacy for backdoor attacks [86]. Blockchain integration for decentralization and transparency [89]–[91].
Systems Heterogeneity	Diverse hardware and resource capacities among devices in 6G networks [97]. Specific hardware requirements [98] and resource-constrained devices (e.g., IoMT) with limited computational demands.	Model compression, quantization, lightweight models (e.g., SNN), edge computing [33], [99]. Adaptive FL algorithms dynamically adjust to resource availability, enhancing inclusivity [100].
Statistical Heterogeneity	Non-IID data distributions across 6G networks [101]. Data volume and type vary significantly between devices. Issues in model convergence and performance due to diverse data sources. e.g., varying sensor types, data collection methods, and user behaviours in 6G [102].	Personalized FL tailored for the diverse and dynamic data sources in 6G [103]. Clustering-based methods to effectively manage and utilize heterogeneous data in 6G [104]. Transfer learning to adapt pre-trained models for specific 6G applications [48]. Balance data contributions for fair participation and robust FL systems in 6G [48].
Concept Drift	Data changes over time due to seasonal variations, user preferences, and rapid technological advancements facilitated by 6G networks [105]. High error rates during drifts in 6G applications decrease after model adaptation using the high-speed connectivity and low latency of 6G networks.	Federated Attention (FedAtt) for dynamic adaptation in 6G networks, leveraging their high-speed connectivity and low latency [105]. Regular model updates with new data through seamless integration capabilities of 6G [106]. FUL for privacy compliance and remove outdated data with secure data handling in 6G [107].

and updates are securely recorded in a tamper-proof ledger, improving transparency and trust between participants [91]. Despite FL's advantage of exchanging model parameters instead of raw data, recent attacks such as membership-inference attacks demonstrate that this approach does not fully guarantee privacy. The FL training process involves communication between clients and the FL server, exposing the model to potential security threats [82]. Furthermore, central servers in many FL architectures can be targeted to aggregate and reconstruct sensitive details from model updates [92]. Therefore, novel privacy-preserving techniques tailored to the unique characteristics and requirements of 6G networks are critically needed in FL. These solutions may include advanced cryptographic techniques [93], noise addition methods, or new FL architectures [94]. In addition, a mimic learning approach has been adopted in FL scenarios to preserve user privacy and prevent reverse engineering attacks. This involves using a teacher model trained on sensitive user data to label a public dataset, which is then used to train a student model. The student model, trained on non-sensitive data, is sent to the centralized server to generate a new global model. This method transfers knowledge without revealing sensitive information, protecting the student model from reverse engineering attacks [95] [96].

(ii) *Systems heterogeneity*: Implementing FL in 6G networks involves addressing significant challenges related to hardware heterogeneity and varying resource capacities. Devices participating in FL can range from powerful smartphones to resource-constrained Internet of Medical Things (IoMT) devices, each with different computational capabilities, memory capacities, and power availability. For instance, some devices' limited power and computational resources can make their participation in the FL process difficult or nearly impossible [97]. Specific hardware requirements are crucial for the effective implementation of FL. As highlighted in the development of next-word prediction for virtual keyboards, devices need at least two gigabytes of available memory to participate efficiently [98]. However, many IoMT devices and other low-power IoT devices do not meet these requirements, having limited memory and computational power. This discrepancy is particularly pronounced in 6G networks, where the diversity of connected devices and their capabilities is even greater. Dealing with such resource-constrained heterogeneous devices

poses a significant challenge. These devices often struggle with the computational demands of training and updating ML models, leading to slower processing times and increased energy consumption. Additionally, the variability in hardware capabilities can result in inconsistent model performance across the network, as some devices may not be able to contribute effectively to the training process. Strategies such as model compression, quantization, lightweight models, and edge computing have been explored to address these challenges. Model compression techniques reduce the models' size, making them more manageable for devices with limited resources. Quantization involves reducing the precision of the model parameters, thereby decreasing the computational load. Edge computing leverages nearby edge servers to offload some processing tasks from the end devices, helping to balance the computational load across the network [33]. A lightweight model such as SNN can reduce the energy consumption of model training [99]. Moreover, adaptive FL algorithms that dynamically adjust to the resource availability of participating devices can improve the inclusivity of FL, allowing even resource-constrained devices to contribute to the learning process [100]. These approaches are particularly relevant in 6G networks, where robust, scalable, and inclusive solutions are critical due to the expected exponential increase in connected devices and data traffic. By addressing the challenges posed by systems heterogeneity, 6G networks can leverage FL to enable advanced applications and services while ensuring efficient and equitable participation across diverse devices [108].

(iii) *Statistical heterogeneity*: Data in 6G networks is often collected and produced in highly non-IID ways across the network. This statistical heterogeneity poses significant challenges for FL. In 6G networks, the diversity of data sources is even more pronounced due to the wide array of devices and applications. The data volume across devices can vary significantly, with some devices generating large amounts of data while others produce very little [101]. Moreover, there may be an inherent statistical structure that describes the connections among devices and their associated data distributions. For example, devices in urban areas might generate different data types than those in rural areas, and devices used by different demographic groups might exhibit varied usage patterns. These non-IID data distributions can lead to issues in model

convergence and performance [102]. Addressing statistical heterogeneity requires the development of advanced FL algorithms that can handle non-IID data effectively. Techniques such as personalized FL [103], where models are tailored to individual device data, and clustering-based methods [104], where devices with similar data distributions are grouped together, can help mitigate these issues. Additionally, transfer learning techniques can transfer knowledge from devices with abundant data to those with scarce data, enhancing overall model performance [48]. Furthermore, strategies to balance the data contributions from different devices are essential. This can involve weighting updates from devices based on the quality and quantity of their data or implementing mechanisms to ensure fair participation from all devices, regardless of their data volume. These approaches aim to create a more robust and equitable FL system that can adapt to the diverse data landscapes of 6G networks. By effectively managing statistical heterogeneity, FL can achieve better model performance and convergence, ensuring that the benefits of ML are realized across the entire spectrum of devices in 6G networks.

(iv) *Concept drift*: In a 6G environment, device-generated data can change due to various factors such as seasonal variations, user preference changes, or technological advancements. The FL models can present high error rates while the drifts take place, and the errors decrease only after the model learns the distributions [105]. For example, a model trained on user data for predicting mobile app usage might become less accurate as new applications are introduced and user preferences shift. Similarly, models for network traffic prediction must adapt to changing patterns due to new devices and applications being added to the network. Addressing the concept drift challenges, the authors in [105] proposed Federated Attention (FedAtt), a variant of the simple FedAvg algorithm that uses dynamically altered coefficients to adapt to drift as quickly as possible. The results showed that attention to FL can handle concept drift and greatly reduce the time taken by a model to reach a stable state after concept drift. Also, regularly updating the models with new data ensures they remain relevant and accurate as the underlying data distribution changes [106]. This involves periodically retraining the models using the latest data from participating devices. In addition, FUL is a crucial technique for addressing concept drift and ensuring privacy compliance [107]. It involves the selective removal of the influence of specific data points or entire datasets from the trained model. This can be particularly important when data becomes outdated, or users request their data be deleted for privacy reasons. FUL ensures that models are up-to-date and respect user data privacy and regulatory requirements. This process typically involves retraining the model with the remaining data or adjusting the model parameters to negate the influence of the removed data. This ensures that FL models will perform well even as the data environment evolves.

IV. SECURITY THREATS FOR FL ENABLED 6G

FL is envisioned as a key enabler in 6G, supporting distributed intelligence while preserving user data privacy. However, integrating FL into 6G introduces a complex security

landscape. To elaborate this in a clear manner, we categorize security threats into three dimensions: (1) FL for 6G, where FL supports 6G; (2) 6G for FL, where 6G features and infrastructures are leveraged to enhance FL; and (3) shared threats, which impact both FL and 6G ecosystems due to their mutual interdependence.

A. Security Threats in FL for 6G

FL enabled 6G networks are vulnerable to various security threats inherent to FL. FL-specific security threats that will be introduced to 6G are illustrated in Fig. 8.

1) *Data Poisoning*: A data poisoning attack in an FL system occurs at the training phase that manipulates the training data used for the local training at the distributed nodes [109]. Various data poisoning efforts include adding adversarial input data and modifying input data such as label-flipping or noising [110]. Local training performed on poisoned data generates poisoned model updates, which are aggregated at the central server while creating the global model for the next iteration. Therefore, the aggregation propagates the poisoning effect to benign distributed clients, too. The benign clients also perform the local training using the poisoned model, which leads to a compromised model after the training process. Poisoning attacks can exist as targeted poisoning attacks and untargeted poisoning attacks [109]. The objective of the targeted poisoning attacks is to attack only a chosen set of inputs and behave normally on all other inputs [84]. Conversely, untargeted poisoning attacks focus on degrading the model performance. It is safe to say that untargeted poisoning attacks are easier to detect than targeted poisoning attacks, as the model performance degradation can be easily visible.

6G era envisions deploying complex, interconnected networks with AI being a core functionality, rather than just an enabler for isolated functions, stepping towards connected intelligence” [3], [111]. Due to the distributed nature of 6G networks and applications, FL techniques are expected to be deployed for network operation and maintenance tasks in RAN, edge, and core layers in addition to the applications. 6G applications demand extreme requirements such as higher data rates (up to 1 Tb/s), extremely low end-to-end latency (< 1 ms), extremely high end-to-end reliability (99.9999%) [?],

Fig. 8: FL-specific attacks that will compromise 6G security

[111]. The trained FL models should also produce outputs to cater to these demands. Therefore, the effect of a poisoned FL system will instantly significantly damage the application before it is detected. Potential RAN layer FL application that monitors intrusions may have its server at the edge. An adversary can feed false data via one 6G base station to poison this FL application at the learning phase, even without having control of the base station. The existing defences against data poisoning attacks are designed for an FL system with n distributed nodes and a single server, whereas, in the 6G era, the FL architectures are expected to change, for example, HFL and DFL. With these FL architectures, data generation may exhibit non-IID behaviours. Thus, the state-of-the-art data poisoning attack detection algorithms [112] might not be optimal.

Possible directions to mitigate: One of the most notable changes in FL in 6G is that the FL architecture will deviate from the current setup of n distributed nodes and a single server. With the new architectures, the server functionality can be brought towards the edge for early detection of data poisoning attacks. For example, hierarchical robust aggregation techniques where the model updates are examined at each layer with possible filtering mechanisms to filter out model updates trained on poisoned data. In other words, an adaptation of FL architecture to 6G network architecture or the application architecture to prevent the propagation of data poisoning effect toward upper layers. Sophisticated sub-sampling techniques that select the nodes participating in the FL process can reduce the data poisoning effect as the poisoning effect has less contribution at the central server aggregation.

2) *Model Poisoning:* A model poisoning attack does not require access to the training data, but only the locally trained model parameters [80]. During a model poisoning attack, the adversary modifies the model parameters so that the poisoned model contributes optimally toward the poisoning objective. In contrast to the data poisoning attacks, whoever receives the model can execute a model poisoning attack. 5G core network service-based architecture will extend in 6G to the Radio Access Network (RAN), named “RAN-core convergence”. It will harmonize the RAN and core functions to create simpler networks [113]. The FL systems will also have redesigned architectures to accommodate these changes. Since the model poisoning does not require any training data for the poisoning task, any compromised node with access to the model can perform a model poisoning attack. With more networks interconnected in 6G, the risk of model poisoning is high due to the sharing of model parameters among networks with different levels of security. O-RAN in 6G uses non-proprietary sub-components from various vendors to form the RAN. The defenses may also differ from vendor to vendor, creating opportunities for model poisoning attacks. Application-level peer-to-peer sharing of model updates is also a key factor that increases the risk of model poisoning, for example, in key 6G applications like autonomous vehicles. In addition, due to the lack of centralized supervision, FL clients may avoid training their own local model and exchange duplicated models [114], [115]. This type of model plagiarism attacks are difficult to

detect and affects model training accuracy and performance.

Possible directions to mitigate: Encrypted model updates prevent the adversary from optimizing the model poisoning attacks toward the poisoning objective. However, the data-generating clients can still poison the model after it is trained using the local data. Sophisticated defence algorithms against model poisoning that use hierarchical clustering methods and filtering can be used to fight against model poisoning attacks. The filtering mechanism should filter out potential poisoned clusters and select the best cluster to proceed with the training process. Split learning techniques train different parts of the FL model at different nodes. Employing split learning techniques can reduce the chance for the adversary to poison the entire model. In addition, [114] proposes a method to add a time-shift pseudo-noise sequence to each client’s local model to minimize plagiarism attacks. Furthermore, a model misconduct detector based on greedy parameter tuning is proposed in [115] that can detect model plagiarism, fabrication and falsification to minimize model poisoning attacks.

3) *Inference Attacks:* Model inference attacks also substantially threaten FL systems in 6G networks [11]. One of the key design goals of FL is to enhance data privacy by keeping the data at the source nodes. The objective of the inference attack is to deduce sensitive information about the training data. Therefore, the main effect of an inference attack is the privacy breach. The inference attacks exist in attribute inference [116] where the adversary tries to infer specific data attributes. Other types of inference attacks include membership inference attacks [117] and model inversion attacks [118]. Membership inference determines whether a specific data sample is used in the training dataset, while model inversion reconstructs the training data samples using model outputs.

6G is a network with tiny cells, mesh networks, multi-connectivity, and sub-networks [11] where there are substantial connections between networks. The interconnected paradigm needs the FL model information transferring among these networks to utilize the intelligence properly. Therefore, an inference attack may expose sensitive information via the network boundaries, putting the sensitive information at further risk. From an application perspective, 6G applications like Wireless Brain-Computer Interactions (BCI) [111] take a step forward in healthcare scenarios where private information leakage via an inference attack will have catastrophic damages. Due to the high degree of automation in 6G, such privacy violations may go unnoticed, leading to further damages in terms of privacy violations.

Possible directions to mitigate: Differential privacy [?], where a certain noise component is added to the models after local model training, is one of the prominent techniques against inference attacks in FL systems. It makes it challenging for the adversaries to infer information about the individual data points. Training the model specific to adversarial inputs also makes the FL system robust against inference attacks. Homomorphic encryption [119], and secure multi-party communication [120] are other techniques that can be employed in FL systems against inference attacks. However, it should be noted that meeting the computational overhead demanded by homomorphic encryption, especially at the network edge, is

a challenge. This demands further research and development work, such as exploring the possibility of utilising Graphics Processing Units (GPUs) and Field Programmable Gate Arrays (FPGAs) in the network edge, as proposed in [121].

4) *Adversarial Aggregator*: The task of an FL system aggregator is to combine all the received models from the distributed users using an aggregation logic and prepare the model for the next iteration. In a conventional FL system with n distributed nodes and a single server, the server is a single point of failure and is generally assumed to be a trusted entity. However, the adverse effect of an aggregator becoming a malicious entity is high as the aggregator can see all the model updates from the distributed users before the aggregation. A poisoning aggregator can create its own poisoned model and distribute it among the users to poison the FL process. An aggregator can also infer statistical information from the receiving models to predict the nature of each FL participant's data. An adversarial aggregator in the 6G edge network can harm the RAN-level FL functions by simply performing a model poisoning attack during the training phase and creating a malicious model.

Possible directions to mitigate: Fully distributed FL systems [122] eliminate the role of the aggregator, thereby removing the single point of failure. This is one of the solutions against adversarial aggregators. Moreover, the aggregation role can be offloaded to a different trusted system like blockchain so no centralized entity can influence the aggregation [123].

5) *Plagiarism Attacks*: An adversary copies or reconstructs the model parameters of a benign client in a federation during a plagiarism attack [114]. Among various FL architectures, systems with peer-to-peer model update sharing are more vulnerable to plagiarism attacks, as neighbors receive model updates directly from peers. The attacker conducts plagiarism attacks by manipulating local updates or training behavior so that the global model incorporates or reveals content identical or extremely similar to a victim's model or dataset. Since 6G aims for distributed intelligence at the edge and device level, plagiarism attacks can significantly harm distributed intelligence and violate data privacy.

Possible directions to mitigate: Adding controlled noise to gradients using differential privacy techniques [94], secure aggregation, gradient compression and obfuscation, and anomaly detection can help detect plagiarism attacks in 6G FL systems.

B. Security Threats in 6G for FL

1) *Node Vulnerabilities*: 6G FL systems comprise a wide variety of 6G devices and nodes, including edge devices, base stations, mobile clients, and IoT devices. These nodes can be inherently vulnerable to a variety of attacks due to their decentralized nature, limited security resources, and exposure to untrusted environments [124]. Node vulnerabilities in 6G can arise from compromised devices, faulty hardware, or weak authentication mechanisms, leading to injecting poisoned data, performing model inversion, or sending incorrect updates to the global model. Attackers might target weak 6G nodes that do not have comprehensive security, get access into them

and manipulate the FL process or to infer from the model parameters.

Possible directions to mitigate: To address node vulnerabilities, FL systems in 6G can implement strong authentication mechanisms at the device level. Techniques such as blockchain-based trust models [125] can also be used. Robust algorithms [126] at FL server also help against node vulnerabilities by where strong security at the node level cannot be implemented. Using secure hardware, such as Trusted Execution Environments (TEEs), for edge and mobile devices can also help protect the integrity of the training data and model updates.

2) *Unreliable Communication Channels*: 6G communication channels are critical for the efficient transmission of model updates between distributed nodes and the FL server. Given the massive number of devices, diverse communication infrastructure, and the demanding use cases in 6G, these channels can sometimes be unreliable. Unreliable communication can be exploited by attackers to introduce various types of security threats, such as eavesdropping [127], Man-In-The-Middle (MITM) attacks [128], or data manipulation.

Possible directions to mitigate: 6G network slicing can be employed to isolate and allocate dedicated resources to FL tasks [63]. With network slicing, FL-related communications can be placed on a low-latency, high-reliability slice of the network, providing a more reliable communication channel with fewer disruptions. Enhancing communication security with encryption and integrity checks is crucial in 6G. Advanced encryption algorithms and techniques, such as homomorphic encryption can be used to protect sensitive model updates during transmission [11]. At the same time, digital signatures and message authentication codes (MACs) can help verify the integrity and authenticity of the data being exchanged.

3) *6G Application Threats*: The wide range of 6G applications ranging from autonomous vehicles to remote surgery, industrial automation are expected to operate in highly dynamic environments with demanding performance requirements such as ultra-low latency, high throughput, and high reliability. These applications also bring additional security threats into the FL systems including data breaches, model poisoning, and adversarial attacks. 6G applications utilizing FL may be targets for attacks aiming to manipulate or steal critical data, mislead the learning process, or compromise application functionality [129].

Possible directions to mitigate: Continuous auditing of FL models and periodic updates to the learning process can ensure that the system is resilient against emerging threats [130]. Regular re-training, model evaluation, and security patches should be applied to address vulnerabilities and improve the robustness of the application over time. A trust-based approach can be introduced to evaluate the reliability of the nodes participating in the FL process [131]. Nodes with a proven track record of honest behavior could be assigned more weight in the aggregation process, while nodes showing suspicious behavior could be excluded or given lower priority.

C. Shared Threats Across FL and 6G

1) *Joint Resource Exploitation*: FL and 6G share critical resources such as bandwidth, compute, and storage. The tight integration of AI into RAN (AI-RAN) [132] in 6G systems can also increase the risk of joint resource exploitation, as attackers may simultaneously target shared computational and communication resources used for both AI-driven network functions and federated learning tasks. Attackers may exploit this overlap through resource exhaustion attacks [133], where, for instance, heavy FL model training leads to degraded service quality on the communication side, or vice versa. An adversary may intentionally inject tasks that consume excessive bandwidth or computation under the guise of FL updates, disrupting both learning and communication services.

Possible directions to mitigate: Implementing resource-aware scheduling [134] and network slicing can help balance computational and communication loads, ensuring efficient resource utilization while maintaining the performance and security of federated learning tasks in 6G networks. Developing cross-layer anomaly detection systems [135] enables the identification of abnormal resource usage patterns across different layers of the 6G network, enhancing the security and robustness of federated learning deployments against joint resource exploitation attacks.

2) *Deployment and Orchestration Threats*: In FL-enabled 6G, large-scale deployment involves coordination across heterogeneous edge nodes, mobile devices, and cloud platforms. These deployments often rely on virtualized environments, dynamic network slices, and automated orchestration tools. Adversaries can exploit misconfigurations, insecure APIs, or privilege escalation in these orchestration layers to disrupt the learning process, gain unauthorized access, or manipulate data and model updates.

Possible directions to mitigate: Zero-trust architectures [136] can enhance the security of FL-enabled 6G deployments by enforcing strict identity verification, continuous authentication, and least-privilege access across all nodes and layers. Isolation techniques [137], such as network slicing and containerization, can limit the potential attacks in FL-enabled 6G systems by separating resources, processes, and communication flows across different network layers and applications.

V. FL FOR 6G NETWORK SECURITY

This section explains FL's role in strengthening 6G security and explores its role in device/IoT security, RAN and O-RAN security, edge network security, orchestration, and core network security (ZSM and cloud-native security). A summary of published work on FL for 6G Security is also presented in Table VI.

A. 6G Device/IoT Security

1) *Introduction*: IoT in 6G networks represents a significant evolution from traditional IoT systems, driven by ambitions to achieve ultra-efficient, secure, and automated industries. Unlike IoT in previous generations, 6G IoT devices operate in an environment characterized by unprecedented scale, diversity, and complexity, alongside the integration of advanced

Fig. 9: FL integration and threat positioning on IoT in 6G

communication, sensing, and computing functionalities. This evolution introduces unique security challenges and requirements that differ fundamentally from earlier IoT deployments. 6G IoT deployments are expected to operate at an unparalleled scale, connecting trillions of devices across diverse applications, ranging from consumer electronics to mission-critical systems like healthcare [138], smart cities [139], and industrial automation. These devices are not just data endpoints but also play an active role in collaborative processing and decision-making, making them highly sensitive to data security, privacy, and integrity issues [140].

In 6G, IoT devices leverage advanced communication technologies such as joint communication and sensing (JCS) and terahertz (THz) communication, which significantly enhance data transmission rates and sensing accuracy. However, these advancements also introduce new attack surfaces, such as susceptibility to jamming and eavesdropping, which were less prominent in earlier networks. Additionally, the AI-native 6G architecture integrates IoT devices directly into distributed learning frameworks, like FL, making these devices critical nodes in the AI pipeline. Any compromise at the device level can jeopardize the global learning model, amplifying the need for robust security mechanisms. Figure 9 provides an overview of the potential threats in IoT deployment scenarios within 6G networks and demonstrates how FL can mitigate these vulnerabilities. A defining characteristic of 6G IoT devices is also their integration into human-centric and critical applications. These include healthcare, autonomous vehicles, and collaborative robots (Cobots), where data breaches or device failures can result in severe societal and economic consequences [141]. Unlike previous IoT deployments, 6G IoT applications demand extreme reliability and security, often involving sensitive data such as patient records or vehicle control parameters. Regulations like HIPAA and GDPR impose stringent requirements on data privacy, further complicating the challenge of maintaining real-time, secure operations in dynamic 6G environments. Another significant distinction is the focus on ultra-low latency and real-time processing in 6G IoT. While traditional IoT networks often rely on centralized AI-based approaches, these methods struggle to meet the sub-millisecond latency requirements of 6G use cases. Applications such as real-time patient monitoring and vehicular communication demand faster processing speeds than centralized architectures can provide [142]. FL addresses this limitation by enabling on-device model training and inference, significantly reducing the reliance on centralized systems and ensuring

low-latency responses. Moreover, the scale and heterogeneity of 6G IoT networks also create unique security challenges. With trillions of interconnected devices, the network becomes susceptible to large-scale DDoS attacks targeting constrained devices or critical infrastructure. Moreover, the diversity of devices, ranging from low-power sensors to high-performance edge nodes, requires adaptable security mechanisms tailored to different device capabilities and application contexts. General IoT systems are not designed to handle this level of diversity and scale. Finally, 6G IoT networks operate within a dynamic and decentralized ecosystem, with devices interacting across edge, cloud, and device layers. This decentralization increases the attack surface while complicating the task of securing inter-device communication. Dynamic network topologies, such as those in vehicular networks, introduce additional challenges for traditional security paradigms, necessitating innovative approaches like FL to ensure robust and flexible security solutions.

In conclusion, 6G IoT devices demand a rethinking of IoT security strategies, focusing on scalability, real-time performance, and resilience against sophisticated threats. FL offers a promising approach to address these challenges by enabling distributed and privacy-preserving intelligence, reducing the reliance on centralized architectures vulnerable to disruption. As depicted in Figure 9, FL plays a pivotal role in mitigating critical security threats in the 6G IoT ecosystem.

2) *How FL helps in improving security:* FL is a promising approach to integrate ML into 6G to enhance device security and privacy. In FL, model training is a collaborative approach that includes multiple local nodes training individually training a local model using the local data, and sharing the local model updates for aggregation. Data privacy is achieved through keeping data localized on the local nodes, ensuring sensitive information never leaves their control, as only model updates are shared instead of the raw data [27]. This important feature of FL eradicates a major integration challenge for 6G, which is envisioned towards human-centric IoT applications [143]. As previously stated, FL does not require data transfers to a centralized location for training. Instead, the local model updates are transferred, yielding an advantage on bandwidth usage. In FL, the local training outcomes will be shared as a local model update, which does not consist of the raw data. This feature is important to align with the scalability requirement in FL, which is envisioned in 6G. In addition, the local training at the edge infrastructure layer [144] is a potential approach that offloads computationally expensive model training into an intermediary edge service and shares the model updates to the cloud.

In FL, a centralized server aggregates the local model updates shared by the local workers and establishes the global model. The global model has been disseminated among the local workers, and real-time response [145] is improved through on-device model updates, enabling rapid response for ML service invocation without directly relying on central server dependencies. The real-time low-latency responsiveness is a distinguishing feature of FL for integrating intelligence in vehicular networks [146] and healthcare applications [147] in 6G. FL is a collaborative ML approach; thereby, it is

Fig. 10: Security-enhanced architecture and enablers for O-RAN

challenging for the adversary to launch a DoS attack and compromise the ML model compared to the centralized ML applications that store the trained models in the cloud [148]. The global model update has been replicated in all the local workers and ensures improved robustness to the adversaries that affect the ML model [149].

3) *Advantages/Disadvantages:* FL enhances privacy and security by allowing devices to train ML models locally without sharing raw data. This is important with the emerging concerns for data privacy on the 6G applications. The reduced data transmission overhead by only sending model updates, which is especially advantageous in 6G's data-intensive environment to cater the envisioned scalability requirements. FL can also enable real-time responses, as models are continuously refined on individual devices, enhancing user experience. However, several challenges in FL must be investigated in future research. FL includes collaborative model updates sharing to the cloud server, and it is challenging to establish trust between the local workers and the cloud server [90]. The adversarial local workers send the model updates based on poisonous data, defined as data poisoning attacks [150]. In addition, when the untrusted local workers send poisonous model updates, defined as model poisoning attack [151], that affects the classification accuracy. Overall, it is important to evaluate the trust of the local workers while considering the model updates.

B. RAN/O-RAN Security

1) *Introduction:* O-RAN represents a significant change in the telecommunications landscape, opening up critical infrastructures previously dominated by a few vendors. As the industry moves to O-RAN, security issues are becoming increasingly important. In this section, we focus on the security aspects of O-RAN as summarized in Fig. 10.

2) *FL for security in RAN/O-RAN:* While identifying specific vulnerabilities is crucial, understanding the broader security landscape and leveraging FL's advantages can contribute to a more robust and resilient beyond 5G ecosystem. In the context of Beyond 5G networks, using Radio Access Network (RAN) and O-RAN brings new challenges and opportunities

TABLE VI: Summary of Related Work on FL for 6G Security

Ref.	Key Contributions	Security Service				
		6G Device/IoT Security	RAN/O-RAN Security	Edge Network Security	Orchestration Security	Core Network Security
[144]	This work proposes an efficient communication approach, "FedCPF", which provides efficiency in local training of vehicular clients that indicates less duration in model convergence with improved test accuracy.	✓				
[148]	This paper proposes a novel model that utilizes differential privacy with a robust mechanism to preserve the privacy of data and the classifier in multiple data owner scenarios.				✓	
[149]	This paper reflects insights on the privacy and robustness of FL with attacks and appropriate defence mechanisms.	✓		✓		
[150]	This paper proposes a novel framework named (AT^2FL) that provides an efficient method and solves the optimal attack problem with an efficient derivation method of implicit gradients for poisoned data.	✓				
[90]	This paper proposes a reputation mechanism for reliable local worker selection with the integration of consortium blockchain.	✓				
[152]	Proposes a model for secure Internet of Medical Things (IoMT) resource recommendation and propagation using federated learning and blockchain technologies	✓				
[153]	proposes a 3GPP-compliant privacy preservation collaborative learning scheme for 6G-NS security, focusing on V2X-NS cross-border areas	✓		✓		
[3]	Develops a model, "Secure5G" based on neural networks for detecting and thereby eliminating the potential threats proactively in a network slice	✓			✓	✓
[154]	Discusses the application of FL in O-RAN environments, focusing on privacy-preserving data processing and collaborative threat detection.		✓			
[155]	Explores RAN slicing and resource optimization in O-RAN using FL, highlighting the benefits of decentralized model updates for enhancing security.		✓			
[156]	Examines the reduction of attack surfaces in O-RAN through FL, emphasizing the distribution of learning processes to mitigate vulnerabilities.		✓			
[157]	Reviews the vulnerabilities in O-RAN components, such as xApps, and discusses how FL can enhance the security posture by mitigating identified risks.		✓			
[158]	Investigates the role of FL in addressing security challenges in the O-RAN SC, with a focus on securing the RIC Message Router (RMR) and E2 interface.		✓			
[97]	Surveys the computational challenges in FL, particularly in devices with limited capacity, and their impact on contributing to global models in ZSM.			✓	✓	
[159]	Reviews group-based FL techniques for efficient model updates, addressing communication overhead in large-scale ZSM deployments.			✓	✓	
[160]	Discusses secure aggregation techniques for FL in hybrid cloud environments, addressing challenges in orchestrating services across diverse cloud platforms.			✓	✓	
[161]	Reviews AI-driven approaches for secure and efficient orchestration in ZSM, highlighting the benefits of FL for dynamic and adaptive service management.			✓	✓	
[162]	Explores the feasibility of FL for secure orchestration in cloud-native environments, focusing on the challenges and solutions for implementation.			✓	✓	

for security and data protection. Incorporating FL into RAN and O-RAN implementations can provide a comprehensive and privacy-preserving solution for the evolving security landscape in Beyond 5G networks. FL plays a central role in overcoming the security challenges in O-RAN environments and is changing the traditional centralised data processing model. In the context of O-RAN security, FL offers specific advantages:

(i) *Data Privacy in O-RAN*: One of the most important advantages is preserving user privacy in O-RAN implementations, which can be achieved through decentralized model training. In the conventional approach, centralized model training raises data protection issues. However, FL enables collaborative training across multiple devices without sharing raw data, protecting sensitive information at the network's edge. This privacy-centric approach aligns with data protection regulations in O-RAN deployments [154], [163]. Differential privacy can also be applied to RAN data by applying noise to individual updates to prevent the extraction of sensitive

information and thus ensure the confidentiality of user data.

(ii) *Reducing Single Point of Failure in O-RAN*: FL increases security by distributing model updates to edge devices, reducing the risk of single points of failure and making the system resilient to local attacks in O-RAN environments. O-RAN introduces the concept of RAN slicing to optimize resources for different services [155]. Secure aggregation techniques in FL ensure that model updates from multiple devices within each RAN slice are combined without exposing individual contributions, maintaining the overall security of the global model.

(iii) *Reduced Attack Surface in O-RAN*: O-RAN, with its diverse ecosystem, benefits from FL's reduction of the overall attack surface. Using FL in O-RAN [156] distributes the learning process and thus reduces the overall attack surface compared to a centralized model with concentrated vulnerabilities.

(iv) *Resilience Against Local Attacks in O-RAN*: The security posture of O-RAN is strengthened by local model updates

of FL, as the compromise of one device does not compromise the entire model and thus limits the impact of potential attacks. The decentralized nature of FL also strengthens the system against adversarial attacks, as attackers need to compromise multiple devices to affect the global model. Open RAN Software Community (O-RAN SC), the open source reference implementation of the O-RAN standards is of unique importance in that aspect [157], [158]. It is being actively developed with contributions from major RAN vendors, including Ericsson, Nokia, Samsung, Radisys and AT&T. xApp can be vulnerable to potential attack vectors due to the open interfaces that allow components from different providers. xApps, being software components with limited integration into hardware, present a potentially easier entry point for malicious actors. Since advanced O-RAN use cases often revolve around xApps, it is important to understand and fix their vulnerabilities. Within *oran-sc*, the security analysis focuses on the RIC Message Router (RMR) and the E2 interface. This choice is justified by the direct interaction of the xApps with these components. Some of the identified vulnerabilities in this context include³:

- *CVE-2023-40998*: A crafted malicious packet from an xApp causes the real-time RIC's E2term to crash. This vulnerability could interrupt communication and jeopardise the real-time functionality of the RIC.
- *CVE-2023-40997*: A crafted message sent in an invalid format causes near-real-time RIC's E2term to crash. Similar to the first CVE, this vulnerability could lead to service interruptions and affect the reliability of near-real-time RIC operation.
- *CVE-2023-41627*: RIC Message Router (RMR) table spoofing. This vulnerability could be exploited to manipulate RMR tables, leading to unauthorized access or manipulation of information.
- *RMR hijacking*: Two xApps sending the same message type with the same subscription ID.

Fixing vulnerabilities in the RIC Message Router (RMR) and in FL's E2 interfaces, for example, can increase security and reduce the risk of attacks, thereby ensuring the robustness of the entire O-RAN ecosystem.

(v) *Dynamic Model Updates and Adaptability in O-RAN*: FL's ability to adapt to dynamic network conditions enables responsive model updates, contributing to improved security and model performance in O-RAN deployments. In the O-RAN, for example, dynamic spectrum sharing (DSS) is crucial for efficient spectrum utilization [164]. The adaptability of FL to dynamic network conditions is particularly advantageous for DSS, as the model can evolve in real-time based on spectrum usage. This increases security by ensuring that the network can quickly adapt to changes in the wireless environment while maintaining privacy through decentralized learning.

(vi) *Collaborative Threat Detection*: O-RAN is essential to developing 5G networks. FL improves the security of 5G NR by enabling collaborative threat detection across many devices and enabling devices to jointly detect and respond to new security threats [165]. It ensures that the global

model incorporates insights from different network elements, strengthening security against evolving threats in the dynamic 5G/6G landscape [166].

(vii) *Reducing Network Latency in O-RAN*: O-RAN often uses edge computing for low-latency applications. The reduced need for constant communication with a central server minimizes network latency and increases the efficiency and security of RAN/O-RAN implementations [167].

(viii) *Interoperability Across Vendor Ecosystems in O-RAN*: The architecture of O-RAN enables the integration of several vendor-specific xApps (applications). The interoperable nature of FL supports collaboration between the ecosystems of providers within the O-RAN environment and ensures secure integration of components from different sources by providing a secure and privacy-preserving framework for the xApp development of each vendor.

(ix) *Regulatory Compliance and Accountability in O-RAN*: O-RAN implementations often include policy-driven security measures to enforce access controls. FL ensures that policies evolve based on collective insights without compromising individual security parameters, contributing to a more adaptable and secure O-RAN environment. Regarding legal compliance, FL's design is aligned with data protection regulations from the outset, reducing the risk of data breaches and improving overall accountability in data processing.

3) *Advantages/Disadvantages*: FL for RAN/O-RAN security involves navigating a delicate balance between security, privacy and performance. There are several potential trade-offs between these key aspects, and understanding them is critical to developing effective and well-rounded FL systems:

(i) *Privacy vs. Model Accuracy*: To protect user privacy, local model updates often add noise or encryption to the data, which can reduce the accuracy of individual updates. Hence, balancing preserving user privacy and maintaining an accurate global model is important. The degree of noise or encryption should be carefully calibrated so as not to compromise the overall model's effectiveness.

(ii) *Local Model Updates vs. Communication Overhead*: Performing local model updates on individual devices reduces the need for frequent communication with a central server, minimizing privacy risks. However, excessive local updates can lead to communication overhead. The balance between the frequency of local updates and the associated communication overhead is crucial. Too frequent updates can degrade network performance, while too infrequent updates can degrade the model's responsiveness to dynamic network conditions.

(ii) *Decentralization vs. System Complexity*: FL's decentralized approach reduces the risk of single points of failure but can make managing a distributed system more complex. Therefore, it is important to find a balance between decentralization and manageability of the system, as overly complex systems can be difficult to monitor and maintain.

(iv) *Security Measures vs. Model Training Efficiency*: Implementing robust security measures, such as secure aggregation, can cause additional computational overhead, affecting the efficiency of model training. Therefore, it is important to balance robust security measures and modeling efficiency.

³Online: https://www.trendmicro.com/es_es/research/23/1/the-current-state-of-open-ran-security.html, Available: December 2023.

Implementing lightweight but effective security protocols is crucial to maintaining acceptable network performance.

(v) *Collaborative Threat Detection vs. Local Autonomy*: Collaborative threat detection relies on the sharing of information between devices, which can raise concerns about preserving local autonomy and data privacy. Developing threat detection mechanisms that balance the need for cooperation with the need to preserve local autonomy is critical. Privacy-preserving techniques, such as federated analytics, can help mitigate this trade-off.

(vi) *Adversarial Resilience vs. Model Complexity*: Improving the model's resistance to adversarial attacks may come with additional model complexity, affecting model performance. It is, therefore, important to find a balance between the simplicity of the model and its resistance to attacks. Regularly updating model defences and monitoring potential attacks can help maintain security without significantly impacting model performance.

(vii) *Interoperability vs. Security Assurance*: O-RAN's open nature encourages a diverse vendor ecosystem, fostering innovation and competition. Open interfaces promote interoperability among components from different vendors, potentially leading to more flexible and cost-effective solutions. However, promoting interoperability between different provider ecosystems in the O-RAN can pose security challenges. The open interfaces in O-RAN increase the potential attack surface, requiring rigorous security measures to mitigate risks. The integration of components from different manufacturers can pose challenges. Therefore, ensuring security while promoting interoperability is crucial. Introducing common security standards and protocols can help mitigate the risks of integrating components from different vendors.

(viii) *Dynamic Model Updates vs. Latency*: Dynamic model updates based on local conditions improve adaptability but can lead to latency in the learning process. A balance between dynamic updates and acceptable latency is essential. Efficient communication protocols and adaptive learning can help minimize latency without compromising system responsiveness.

C. Edge Network Security

1) *Introduction*: Emerging 6G applications such as VR, AR, and vehicular communication expect an increased utilization of edge networks in 6G due to the close proximity of computation [168]. The explosive growth of smart devices in 6G also brings many distributed computational resources to the edge. Dynamic resource sharing, distributed device-to-device caching, and joint edge computation offloading are a few of the many services the edge layer offers now and will be there in 6G networks. FL-based learning applications to support critical use cases such as autonomous driving also consider Edge as a potential place to implement the FL central server. For example, the Road Side Units (RSU) is the parameter server in FL training for vehicular communications [144]. The architectural changes such as Open-RAN will also add more complexity to the edge networks in 6G networks [169]. The importance of edge as a pivotal element of 6G network architecture and applications, as well as the security of edge, is

extremely important and must be considered carefully before deploying services in edge to support 6G applications. Moreover, the complexity of 6G architecture makes the security provision a challenging task due to the multi-connectivity of networks, the definition of sub-networks, and RAN core convergence [11] in which edge also plays a crucial role. AI-based security in 6G will be an effective approach to complement the existing security mechanisms, as its tolerance against zero-day attacks due to behavioural-based detection. FL is one of the prominent training techniques of such AI-based security mechanisms due to its effective bandwidth utilization and the privacy preservation aspect of data [11]. The flexibility FL provides in its deployment of the parameter server (ex, cloud, edge) makes FL an attractive option in edge network security implementations.

2) *How FL helps in improving security*: Intrusion detection for wireless edge networks based on FL [170] proposes a FL-based Attention Gated Recurrent Unit (FedAGRU) instead of sharing raw data towards a centralized server to train. The edge devices act as the data generating nodes and train an FL model with a parameter server, which is used to prevent poisoning attacks by a compromised edge device in a later stage. FedAGRU analyzes the system's performance in terms of the detection accuracy and the communication cost. FedAGRU improves detection accuracy by approximately 8% and its communication cost is 70% less than other FL algorithms. A lightweight and secure FL scheme for edge computing (LSFL) [171] designs a system against compromised edge nodes. The system provides both secure aggregation and secure Byzantine robustness. LSFL specifically considers the scenario where the edge nodes have limited computing power and the possibility of frequent dropouts during the training process. The design includes a Lightweight two-server secure aggregation protocol, which utilizes two servers to enable secure Byzantine robustness and model aggregation. Spam detection is an important element in security provision. Early detection of spam at the edge helps eliminate the threat at a lower network layer. Also, it reduces unnecessary traffic towards the higher layers of the network, such as the core network and the cloud. FedLearnSP [172] aims to provide security and privacy using FL for edge computing. FedLearnSP trains a model using FL that detects malicious spam images and can be deployed on the edge to identify spam at the inference stage. Cellular vehicle-to-everything (C-V2X) systems are critical systems that need faster responses. Failure to detect an intrusion in such a system can do substantial damage. A new IDS for C-V2X networks based on FL is proposed in [173]. It leverages edge computing to not only build a prediction model in a distributed way but also to enable low-latency intrusion detection. The proposed system can detect DoS, DDoS, and botnets, eliminate them, and provide a secure edge platform for V2X applications. FedGame, a method of utilizing FL with game theory to secure the IoT applications deployed in edge, is presented in [174]. FedGame is a two-stage distributed collaborative architecture that leverages MEC and FL to allow multiple MEC-based domains to build an efficient learning model collaboratively. FedGame FL to build an MEC-enabled prediction model for

intrusion detection. In addition, once an intrusion is detected, a noncooperative game is established between MEC nodes to ensure the provisioning of the required virtual resources to deal with the attack. Securing edge-based vehicular networks using FL and blockchain technologies is presented in [175]. The authors propose a two-stage IDS by leveraging FL through multiple edge vehicles and roadside facilities that collaborate together. The trust calculation and block verification algorithm design is driven by model quality. This work analyzes common attacks and shows that the proposed scheme achieves cooperative privacy preservation for vehicles while reducing communication overhead and computation costs.

3) *Advantages/Disadvantages:* By design, FL trains the model locally, but the effect of all the locally trained models is aggregated on the server. The aggregation combines the effects of all the models even though the data generation at each node is non-IID. If an edge server trains a model from its own data and uses it for inference, the scope of the threats the model learns may be limited. The computation requirement to perform the learning can be distributed with FL instead of transferring large amounts of data into a central location and training there. Effective utilization of edge resources can be achieved with FL. Privacy preservation is a design goal of FL where the data-generating nodes keep the data without sending it outside. This is especially helpful in case sensitive information is used for the training.

FL is vulnerable to certain attacks, such as poisoning attacks, compared to centralized training. As the aggregator does not see the data, the aggregator needs to trust the model updates sent by the distributed nodes. If a certain edge node is compromised, the model update from that edge node will be malicious, and the malicious effect will be aggregated and passed to other edge nodes at the next learning iteration. Therefore, additional robust techniques must be implemented to safeguard FL-based edge systems from attacks that add extra overhead to the server. Section IV provides a detailed description of such attacks.

D. Orchestration and Core Network (ZSM and Cloud-Native)

1) *Introduction:* The orchestration and management of core network functions have become increasingly complex in the era of advanced telecommunications, characterised by ZSM and the adoption of cloud-native architectures. ZSM solutions, along with cloud-native principles in Beyond 5G networks, aim to automate and streamline network operations to ensure efficient and secure service delivery [176]–[178]. As summarized in Fig. 11, in the field of ZSM, where automating the provision of network services is of paramount importance, FL offers a unique solution to make the complicated management of services efficient, secure and compliant with data protection regulations. In deploying and managing services in a 5G/6G network, where various edge servers play a crucial role, FL can be applied to these edge servers to learn together and adapt to the dynamic demands of service provisioning [179]. With orchestration techniques, services can remain efficient and responsive, even in highly distributed and complex network environments [180], [181]. As networks evolve into cloud-

Fig. 11: Orchestration and core network management with FL in ZSM and cloud-native architectures

native architectures, the challenges of managing containerized applications and microservices are becoming increasingly complex [182], [183]. FL, applied to orchestrate these cloud-native components, can enable adaptive fault detection and resolution [184], [185]. For example, various microservices can contribute locally to improving fault detection models so that the system can adapt independently to changing conditions and improve the network's overall security [186], [187].

2) *How FL helps in improving security:* FL can play a crucial role in developing and deploying secure and privacy-preserving ZSM solutions. First, FL allows developing ZSM models without centralizing sensitive operational data [15]. To further protect sensitive operational details during model updates, differential privacy techniques can also be applied while relying on cloud nativeness [188]. Secondly, FL enables network elements to jointly improve ZSM functionality by enabling secure collaboration between network elements [16]. In addition, microservices can improve the security service while enabling interaction with edge and cloud services [189]. Third, FL can improve fault detection and resolve mechanisms in ZSM [190]. The global ZSM model benefits from various insights that improve its ability to detect and resolve faults. Further improvements such as the embedding of Explainable AI (XAI) or Blockchain-based Self-Sovereign Identity can increase the explainability of models [191] or identity management of FL clients [192], [193] respectively. Fourth, FL improves service assurance through collaborative learning in the context of ZSM [194]. The global ZSM model can learn from decentralized contributions to improve its ability to ensure quality of service while preserving the privacy of operational information. Fifth, FL ensures secure decision-making processes within the ZSM [195]. Encrypted communication and secure aggregation techniques can ensure that decision-

related information remains confidential and thus contribute to secure and privacy-preserving ZSM operations. Finally, ZSM solutions developed with FL can ensure compliance with data protection regulations by using privacy-preserving techniques.

3) *Advantages/Disadvantages*: FL is an innovative approach with clear advantages and challenges. The privacy-preserving nature of FL is a key advantage as it enables decentralized model training and orchestration in ZSM while protecting sensitive operational details. For example, different network elements such as containerized applications and microservices can train models together so that the system can evolve dynamically in response to real-time insights [161], [162], [186], increasing the security and resilience of the network [196]. The decentralized model promotes collaboration and resilience, reduces dependence on central servers and improves the system's adaptability. However, challenges such as limited local training capabilities, difficulties in handling non-IID data, model synchronization challenges, communication overhead, and the complexity of secure aggregation techniques must be carefully considered. For example, orchestrating services across hybrid cloud infrastructures involves different components such as Kubernetes clusters and public cloud platforms, making it difficult to securely aggregate models [160]. Devices or network elements with limited computational capacity or compromised local devices may face challenges when training local models, affecting their meaningful contribution to the global model [97]. Furthermore, it can be challenging to ensure the synchronization of models across different network elements, especially regarding different hardware capacities and network conditions. The role of FL in promoting interoperability in cloud-native environments is remarkable. It allows different components to contribute to a common model while addressing data transfer and communication security concerns. However, the frequent exchange of model updates could impact the efficiency of orchestration processes, especially in scenarios where large models need to be exchanged [159].

VI. FL FOR 6G APPLICATION SECURITY

The extreme network capabilities envisaged with B5G communication networks enable next-generation applications, including CAV, UAV, advanced healthcare, Industry 5.0, and metaverse/AR/VR. These applications extend from existing paradigms, creating a new threat and security landscape. This section explores how FL enables security and privacy in B5G applications.

A. CAV and UAV

Connected Autonomous Vehicles (CAVs) and Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) are two of the emerging applications harnessing the extreme communication capabilities realized through 6G networks to revolutionize next-generation transportation technologies [3]. The development of vehicles from autonomous driving vehicles to Internet of Vehicles (IoV) drives the next evolution towards CAVs. On the other hand, use cases of UAVs are growing towards many applications, ranging from disaster relief, agriculture, delivery, traffic monitoring,

and security. Both CAVs and UAVs develop on extreme B5G network capabilities, such as extremely low latency, extremely high availability/reliability, and edge AI. FL overcomes the limitations of centralized learning techniques, such as high latency and privacy concerns, by pushing the learning process to edge devices (i.e., CAVs and UAVs). This allows them to train ML models locally on their own private data and then share the model updates, instead of raw data, with a central server for global model aggregation. FL also enhances the capabilities of CAVs in traffic and path prediction. This entails deploying models directly on edge devices, such as vehicles and drones, utilizing their specific datasets encompassing factors like road geometry, traffic patterns, and weather conditions [197]. Similarly, the fusion of FL and 6G networks holds significant potential for UAVs in improving mission-critical applications such as aerial surveillance, environmental monitoring, and disaster management. By harnessing the capabilities of FL, UAVs can collaboratively train ML models, leading to more effective decision-making and autonomous control. For instance, methods such as Air-Ground Integrated FL (AGIFL) combine air and ground networks with FL, where aerial nodes such as UAVs can train FL models in collaboration with ground network nodes [198].

1) *How FL helps in improving security*: FL is a key enabler of enhancing the security and privacy of CAVs and UAVs [20]. CAVs must handle multi-Gbps data streams for cooperative sensing and manoeuvring functionalities [199]. Being a vehicle moving at high speeds and across various geographical locations, communicating large volumes of data with centralized computing resources such as a cloud is not feasible and secure. As a solution, FL can distribute the ML processes across network edge devices, such as vehicles and roadside units, to facilitate the sharing of critical insights while safeguarding data privacy. This cooperative approach helps preserve privacy and enhances decision-making for autonomous driving systems, contributing to safer and more efficient transportation.

FL relying on a centralized server for global model aggregation can become a bottleneck, especially with many vehicle-to-everything (V2X) network participants. As a solution, DFL techniques exploit a fully distributed network architecture without relying on a centralized server, enhancing security and privacy [34]. Furthermore, [200] introduces an autonomous blockchain-based FL design for a privacy-aware and efficient vehicular communication network. Blockchain-based FL enables on-vehicle ML without centralized coordination by availing the consensus mechanism of blockchain [201].

In addition, centralized data processing platforms and even FL that rely on a central entity for continuous aggregation have a single point of failure, which can be targeted by attackers. As a solution, [202] proposes a decentralized FL technique for UAV networks, namely DFL-UN, which enables FL within UAV networks without a centralized entity. With DFL-UN, FL is conducted over different UAVs in a fully distributed manner, where each UAV not only trains a local FL model over its own data and aggregates local models from one-hop neighboring UAVs and broadcasts the resulting model. Additionally, DFL-UN also preserves data privacy. Further-

more, [203] proposes a dispersed FL model for CAVs to enhance privacy while enhancing the robustness and efficiency of communication resource utilization.

2) *Advantages/Disadvantages:* It is clear that FL enhances security and privacy in CAV and UAV applications, as training data remains on local nodes. FL also supports the distributed nature of CAVs and UAVs. Adopting decentralized FL using blockchain further strengthens security and privacy against attacks targeting centralized or isolated nodes. However, FL requires communication with a global model aggregation point or collaboration with other network nodes, resulting in significant communication overhead. Additionally, both FL and decentralized FL involve exchanging large volumes of model parameters, which may be exploited by malicious participants. FL techniques for CAVs and UAVs must also account for the fact that these systems are vulnerable to attacks and intrusions, potentially compromising security and privacy. Future research can address these challenges to fully realize the benefits of FL in securing CAVs and UAVs in B5G networks.

B. Healthcare

1) *Introduction:* FL enables collaborative model training while preserving the privacy of individual raw data used to train the models. ML has a strong potential to extend intelligence for various healthcare applications. FL eliminates the limitations of cloud-based systems with extended capabilities to leverage health information management [204], online diagnosis [205], data analysis [206], and digital healthcare monitoring [207]. FL guarantees the privacy of the individual collaborators in the learning ecosystem by storing raw data on users' individual devices, and only model updates are shared with the centralized server for aggregation and formulation of the global model.

2) *How FL helps in improving security:* The training of ML models in FL comprises a training phase on the individual devices, creating a model based on the locally trained data and sending the local model updates of all individual devices to the cloud server to create the global model based on the local model updates. Furthermore, the cloud server disseminates the global model based on the local model updates aggregated in the global model establishment. In [146], the authors proposed to preserve the privacy of raw data in local training and apply differential privacy to ensure the confidentiality of the classification model. The work in [208] proposed an FL-based framework that preserves side-channel attacks for sensitive healthcare data, including clinical notes, personal information, usernames, and passwords. Lakhan et al. [209] proposed an FL-based framework that integrates blockchain for the fraud identification and privacy preservation of healthcare data. [210] proposed blockchain and local differential privacy integrated framework for medical data sharing. The primary feature of decentralization in FL is increased integration potential with scalability and improved security that does not share sensitive data beyond the local nodes.

3) *Advantages/Disadvantages:* The improved privacy is the most distinguishing feature of FL that increases the integration of blockchain with application scenarios such as blockchain

Fig. 12: Security issues in Industry 5.0

that incorporates sensitive information. In addition, data ownership preservation is much more convenient in FL, even though the local workers share the model updates instead of sharing data. These benefits enhance compliance with regulatory requirements and adaptability to a privacy-sensitive context such as healthcare. In addition, FL increases the collaborative incorporation of multiple organizations while preserving privacy. The key limitations of FL include the significantly larger communication overhead in iterative training, which utilizes the network for local model updates and global model establishment. Generally, FL includes bidirectional communication between the local workers and the cloud server. From the perspective of security, the cloud server that aggregates the global model updates emerges with a risk of being a central point of failure. The consistency of aggregation processes in local workers and the cloud server lacks transparency, creating a risk of identifying poisoning attacks.

C. Industry 5.0

1) *Introduction:* FL plays a prominent role in Industry 5.0 [26] with distributed collaborative and privacy-enhanced ML [211]. FL enables collective intelligence for Industry 5.0 applications, including smart manufacturing [211], logistics [212], and energy management [213]. Intelligent industrial systems incorporate data-driven insights with ML to optimize manufacturing processes with improved efficiency and global sustainability. FL leverages the Industry 5.0 systems to incorporate intelligence into the heterogeneous distributed ecosystems with preserved privacy and provisions for scalability. Security issues in Industry 5.0 is illustrated in Fig. 12. Strengthening security and privacy increases the potential of adaptability of innovations that improve the values of Industry 5.0.

2) *How FL helps improve security:* FL improves the security and privacy of Industry 5.0 applications. [174] proposed FedGame, a game theory and FL-based framework that enables multiple MEC domains to collaborate securely to deal with an IIoT attack with preserved privacy on IoT devices. [214] proposed an FL and blockchain-integrated framework to establish trustworthiness in energy management applications. [215] explained the potential of adaptation of FL for the privacy preservation of digital twin applications, including the

smart city, governance, and Industry 5.0 contexts. Khan et al. [216] proposed an FL-based framework for data poisoning prevention in edge computing. [217] strengthen privacy on data sharing with the integration of FL for intelligent EV energy prediction, which requires sharing data. [218] leveraged FL to collaboratively train a shared AI model without revealing the local energy consumption data, thereby preserving the privacy of energy users. Overall, FL advances the security and privacy of Industry 5.0 systems using the core properties of FL, which shares only the model updates beyond the local workers. The envisioned decentralized service deployment model that deploys heterogeneous IoT devices across the physical surfaces of industrial ecosystems ideally aligns with FL's distributed and collaborative ML paradigm to advance the learning process.

3) *Advantages/Disadvantages*: The key benefit of FL is the improved privacy that guarantees the raw data will not be revealed beyond the local nodes. That feature increases the adaptability of FL to the human-centric Industry 5.0 applications [219] that have strong privacy requirements. In addition, distributed learning provides insights from a wider variety of collaborators that sharpens the ML application.

The communication overhead is one of the major limitations of FL from the perspective of Industry 5.0. The heterogeneous local workers of the Industry 5.0 applications deployed across the network incur a significant network overhead in bi-directional model establishment communication. In addition, the networks with intermittent connectivity between the cloud server and the local workers may formulate biased model updates due to the absence of several collaborators in the network.

D. Metaverse/ AR/ VR

1) *Introduction*: The metaverse is a virtual multiuser environment that merges physical reality with digital virtuality [220]. Combining many technologies makes the metaverse possible, such as VR, digital twins, and AR. Here, the users interact with each other through a virtual representation named "avatars" [221]. Metaverse needs various AI-based services to perform tasks through AR/VR devices, such as identifying user movements, facial emotion recognition, and object detection. At the same time, metaverse will critically require low latency communication to perform the operations through B5G/6G wireless networks, providing connection to the headsets, maintaining coherence with the sensors, and capturing devices to provide a realistic user experience. Hence, FL is identified as a key enabler of Metaverse/ AR/ VR applications in 6G networks.

2) *How FL helps in improving security*: FL can help in metaverse AI-based services to train and collaborate among many devices and across multiple services without revealing their private information [8]. The work in [222] uses a hierarchical FL-based anomaly detection model for smart healthcare using digital twins of the original patients. Considering the IoT devices associated with metaverse, FL-based anomaly detection for IoT is proposed in [223] using Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) models. FL's key feature in constructing

Fig. 13: Metaverse-related adversarial attacks with FL

anomaly detection ML models is the distributed nature and privacy protection for data, where metaverse IoT devices can collaborate without exposing their data or identity for enhancing the robustness of the ML models for detecting anomalies against attacks such as data poisoning.

3) *Advantages/Disadvantages*: A distributed learning and detection process is crucial for the metaverse as billions of future users may utilize the metaverse services. Therefore, FL primarily provides a privacy-preserved architecture for AI in metaverse applications. However, on the downside, FL training within the IoT wearable devices may degrade the performance of these devices if users are using them at that time. Unlike conventional IoT devices, they may have higher active usage time, where users actively engage with the device. Full device capacity may be required to operate the functions with acceptable user experience. Furthermore, the data that the users generate from these wearables will be highly sensitive and directly relevant to a natural person and will be generated in real time. This can attract an adversary for potential attacks on the user's privacy [224]. Fig. 13 provide examples of threats like adversarial poisoning, inference and data reconstruction attacks that can affect metaverse services [224], [225]. Here, the VR headsets and wearables can be compromised by an attacker, or the attacker may be portrayed as a benign user to inject malicious updates to the server from the client side. On a larger scale, the attacker can launch their own third-party service with VR or AR experiences, where the service itself may consist of a malicious server which can inspect model updates. To mitigate this, we can identify three main actions: 1) strengthening the security and privacy measures for the client devices and the communication channel, 2) having a robust assessment of client models from the server side, 3) monitoring and assessing the quality of VR/AR-based ML services, their permissions and security measures by regulatory authorities, due to the high sensitive nature of temporal and spatial data used in these services. Thus, several technological and privacy measures may need to be established when using FL in the metaverse and wearable-associated AI services.

E. Other Applications

1) *Introduction*: There are many other applications for integrating FL into mobile infrastructure to solve security and privacy issues as 6G networks are expected to bring

significant advances in connectivity. Applications that rely on secure authentication and access control, privacy-preserving surveillance and monitoring, privacy-preserving location-based services, cybersecurity for smart cities, privacy-preserving financial transactions, privacy-preserving AI assistants and mobile crowdsensing (e.g. on social networks) are some of the other application areas of FL to improve security and privacy.

2) *How FL helps in improving security:* In secure authentication and access control, multi-factor authentication and access control in critical infrastructures, such as financial institutions or government facilities, where FL enables devices to learn together and improve the accuracy of access control models without compromising individual user credentials [226], [227]. For privacy-preserving surveillance and monitoring, city-wide surveillance systems, where FL enables cameras and sensors to work together to detect security threats and anomalies without transmitting sensitive visual data to a central server, thus protecting citizens' privacy [228]. For adaptive threat detection and response in network security applications in large organisations, FL enables the various devices on the network to learn and respond to emerging cyber threats adaptively, improving the overall resilience of the organisation's cybersecurity infrastructure [229], [230]. For privacy-preserving location-based services that use location-based advertising and recommendations applications in retail environments, FL enables mobile devices to learn user preferences and behaviour together for personalized services without sharing individual location data [231]–[233]. For cybersecurity in smart cities, in security monitoring in smart city deployment applications, FL enables IoT devices and sensors to collaboratively learn and detect cybersecurity threats, ensuring the security and privacy of residents and municipal services [20], [26], [234]–[237]. For privacy-preserving financial transactions, online banking and financial institutions applications use FL to facilitate the development of fraud detection models by enabling devices to collectively learn patterns of fraudulent transactions without revealing individual transaction details [238]–[241]. For privacy-preserving AI assistants on mobile devices applications, FL enables collaborative learning for natural language processing and other AI functions without transmitting sensitive user interactions to a central server, thereby preserving user privacy [242], [243]. For collaborative network intrusion detection in large-scale network environments, such as telecom-specific edge/cloud applications, FL enables devices at the network edge to collaboratively share insights about potential network intrusions, improving the development of adaptive and robust intrusion detection systems [244], [245]. Federated learning-based mobile crowdsensing applications enable the development of a virtual tourism ecosystem in [246].

3) *Advantages/Disadvantages:* The applications of FL in 6G networks for security and privacy offer several advantages but also pose some challenges. FL improves model accuracy without compromising user data and ensures reliable multi-factor authentication in secure authentication and access control. However, there can be challenges in managing the communication overhead and complexity associated with different access control models. For privacy-preserving surveillance and

monitoring, FL enables intelligent threat detection without centralized visual data processing, increasing security in smart city environments. Nevertheless, ensuring model synchronization and dealing with potential biases in surveillance models is a major challenge. In adaptively detecting and responding to threats, FL's adaptability strengthens cybersecurity, but the potential for Byzantine attacks requires robust mechanisms. When analyzing confidential data, FL ensures collaborative research without centralizing sensitive data. Compliance with regulations and maintaining model accuracy are the biggest challenges. With privacy-preserving location-based services, FL improves personalization without compromising individual location data, but finding an optimal compromise between model accuracy and privacy remains a challenge. In secure mobile crowdsourcing applications, FL contributes to security without jeopardising the privacy of communication. However, the challenges lie in managing communication latency and ensuring a real-time response to threats. Cybersecurity for smart cities benefits from FL's collaborative learning, but securing a diverse ecosystem of IoT devices and managing model interpretability remains a problem. FL improves fraud detection without revealing transaction details for financial transactions, but regulatory compliance and preventing adversarial attacks are challenges. For privacy-preserving AI assistants, FL improves natural language processing without compromising interaction with the user. However, the interpretability of the models and ensuring sufficient device resources for local training pose a challenge. Finally, collaborative network intrusion detection benefits from FL's distributed approach, but reaching a consensus on threat definitions and mitigating potential model poisoning attacks is an ongoing challenge. Overall, the benefits of FL in 6G security applications are significant, but overcoming the challenges related to communication overhead, model accuracy, privacy concerns, and security robustness is critical for successful implementation.

VII. LESSONS LEARNED, PROJECTS AND FUTURE RESEARCH DIRECTIONS

This section formulates lessons learned, projects, and remaining research questions and possible future directions on FL for 6G security.

A. FL for 6G Security

1) *Lessons Learned:* FL distributes model updates to the network edge and edge devices, which also minimises the possibility of single points of failure. As a result, FL also strengthens the security of a network against DoS and DDoS attacks. Therefore, FL is proving itself as an enabler of 6G security in a wide area, including 6G device security, IoT Security, RAN/O-RAN security, edge network security, and orchestration/core/ZSM and cloud-native security. In addition to the conventional FL system with n distributed nodes and a single server, hierarchical FL systems and fully distributed FL systems are emerging to utilize the network resources better and to serve critical applications in 6G, like vehicular communication. State-of-the-art research mostly considers

TABLE VII: Summary of Related Work on FL for 6G Application Security.

Ref.	Key Contributions	Application Security				
		CAV/UAV	Healthcare	Industry 5.0	Metaverse/AR/VR	Smart Cities
[203]	Proposes a dispersed federated learning model for CAVs for FL robustness, efficient communication resource utilization and privacy preservation	✓				✓
[199]	Surveys state of the art of vehicular communication and research directions	✓				
[34]	Reviews DFL concepts, frameworks, and challenges	✓	✓	✓		
[200]	Proposes a DFL technique for CAVs	✓				
[201]	Reviews FL technologies and applications	✓		✓		
[202]	Proposes DFL architecture for UAV Networks	✓				
[222]	Proposes a hierarchical FL-based anomaly detection for digital twins		✓	✓	✓	✓
[223]	Designs an anomaly detection technique for FL to identify and classify IoT-based security attacks.	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
[224]	Provides potential privacy risks and reconstruction-based attacks on local ML models used in metaverse-related FL services.				✓	
[225]	Surveys a set of security and privacy risks in the metaverse, including personal information leakage, unauthorised access, and eavesdropping.				✓	

conventional FL systems, and the research related to novel architectures is still emerging. The threat surface can also differ substantially with the emergence of these architectures. For example, hierarchical FL architectures perform intermediate aggregations. Therefore, multiple nodes will act as aggregators in 6G networks, reducing the amount of model updates available to the server to apply state-of-the-art algorithms. Moreover, P2P FL systems directly share the model updates with peers, increasing the chance for poisoning and inference.

2) *Remaining Research Questions*: Despite proving to be a significant contender for strengthening 6G security, the following research questions regarding deploying FL-enabled 6G security remain to be addressed.

- How can FL architectures ensure robust protection against hierarchical and peer-to-peer attacks in emerging 6G network paradigms?
- How can lightweight, adversarial-resilient algorithms used in FL balance the need for ultra-low latency in applications such as autonomous vehicles?
- What cryptographic techniques can simultaneously ensure quantum resistance and efficiency in FL-enabled 6G networks?
- How can FL models be validated to detect poisoned or adversarial updates from compromised devices in 6G networks?
- How to synchronize local models across different 6G network elements and devices?
- How to minimise the communication overhead and increase the efficiency of orchestration processes in 6G networks when large models are exchanged?
- How to optimise the balance between decentralization, communication overheads and efficient/secure model management in 6G networks?

B. FL in 6G Security Projects

Several research projects focus on realizing the potential of FL to secure 6G and 6G applications. For instance, *SPATIAL: Security and Privacy Accountable Technology Innovations, Algorithms, and ML* [247] is a project that focuses on enhancing security and privacy in AI-driven solutions, particularly for

6G networks. It aims to establish transparent and accountable AI practices through the development of metrics, privacy methods, and verification tools. The initiative addresses AI transparency, resilience in decentralized AI deployment, adoption guidelines, education for AI professionals, and clear communication frameworks. Additionally, *SPATIAL* prioritizes data privacy, resilience engineering, and ethical accountability, aligning with EU standards, and seeks to set the foundation for AI security governance in Europe. *Confidential6G: Confidential Computing and Privacy-preserving Technologies for 6G* [248] is another project that aims to fortify data security and privacy in three areas: while in use, in transit, and at the edge, leveraging innovations like Confidential Computing, post-quantum cryptography, and blockchain technologies. The project's foundation rests on post-quantum cryptography, confidential Computing, and confidential communication. In addition, projects such as, *PAROMA-MED* [249] aims to create a hybrid-cloud platform ensuring privacy and security for services in federative cross-border settings, particularly in 6G networks. *FeatureCloud* [250] is another project that aims to enhance the security and privacy of big data in healthcare by introducing a transformative security-by-design concept. This project integrates FL with blockchain technology for privacy-preserving data mining and management of patient rights, allowing patients to revoke consent whenever they choose. Furthermore, the *FRONTIER* [251] project aims to revolutionize computer vision by creating models for embodied perception, which focus on systems that operate within a dynamic 3D world. Specifically, *FRONTIER* will implement FL techniques that facilitate knowledge sharing across different embodied systems, enhancing scale, model accuracy, and robustness beyond what any single system can achieve.

C. Emerging Research Directions of FL in 6G Applications

1) *Quantum-Safe Federated Learning for 6G*: The advent of quantum computing presents dual opportunities and challenges [252]. Quantum FL frameworks, such as those leveraging quantum-safe algorithms, can accelerate local model training [253]. However, the financial and computational costs

associated with quantum nodes necessitate the development of scalable, cost-effective systems [254] [255] [256]. Ensuring the security of FL in quantum-dominated environments requires cryptographic innovations that can withstand quantum decryption capabilities, e.g. post-quantum cryptography solutions of NIST [257].

2) *Green Computing for FL in 6G*: Green computing aligns seamlessly with 6G’s sustainability goals [258]. FL’s ability to perform decentralized learning minimizes the need for energy-intensive data transmissions [259] [260]. Recent studies have highlighted energy-efficient model training techniques that prioritize reduced carbon footprints [261]. Future research should focus on designing cryptographic methods that align with FL’s green computing objectives, ensuring both security and sustainability.

3) *Explainable AI in FL for 6G Security*: XAI is emerging as a critical component of 6G security, providing transparent insights into FL model decision-making, using techniques such as poisoning detection with post-hoc Shapley value explainers [262] and intrusion detection [263]. However, balancing the explainability-privacy trade-off is a significant challenge [264], [265]. Future work should aim to develop XAI frameworks that maintain high privacy standards while delivering actionable insights for intrusion detection and anomaly prevention [266].

4) *Integration with Advanced 6G Architectures and Techniques*: The emergence of hierarchical and peer-to-peer FL architectures necessitates tailored security mechanisms. These architectures introduce new attack surfaces but also offer opportunities for intermediate aggregations to enhance robustness. Novel lightweight algorithms designed for these architectures can address the specific latency, scalability, and privacy requirements of 6G applications. Furthermore, integrating blockchain with FL can be explored as a viable solution towards minimizing communication cost and strengthening resource allocation, security and privacy of FL [26].

5) *Federated multimodal learning for cross-domain data fusion*: Multimodal federated learning [267] has been applied in various domains to protect user privacy in AI applications. In the 6G environment, multimodal devices are more susceptible to data fusion attacks [268] [269]. However, current FL defense strategies are designed for specific methods, and those developed for a single modality are not suitable for multimodal FL [270]. Therefore, transferring single-modality FL defense strategies to multimodal FL is an important research direction.

6) *Federated LLM fine-tuning for on-device large-scale intelligence*: The goal is to collaboratively adapt LLMs across distributed devices while preserving data privacy, making this approach a promising paradigm for intelligent and secure 6G networks. Existing studies on FL for 6G indicate that FL is a key enabler of privacy-aware distributed intelligence. However, current research primarily focuses on conventional models and highlights unresolved challenges in robustness, communication efficiency, and security against adversarial updates, as noted in recent 6G-FL surveys [271]. Future research

should investigate security-aware FL fine-tuning mechanisms specifically for LLMs, including robust aggregation, efficient parameter-efficient updates, and joint optimization of learning performance and 6G network security.

VIII. CONCLUSION

FL is considered a promising candidate for securing 6G, given the inherently distributed architecture of 6G networks. This paper presents a comprehensive survey on federated learning-enabled 6G Security. Initially the paper provides a brief overview of FL and envisaged 6G networks to provide insights into the role of FL in 6G. Then, the paper explores threats in FL for 6G, threats in 6G for FL, and shared threats across FL and 6G. Subsequently, the role of FL in 6G security is explored, considering 6G device/IoT security, RAN/O-RAN security, edge network security, and orchestration and core network. FL for 6G application security are then explored, focusing on applications ranging from CAV, UAV, healthcare, and Industry 5.0 to metaverse/AR/VR. Subsequently, the lessons learned, projects, remaining research questions, and possible future directions towards utilizing FL as a promising technology to strengthen security in emerging 6G networks and applications are presented. It is envisaged that this survey will be instrumental in facilitating future research, development and standardization attempts towards realizing FL-enabled 6G security in 6G networks.

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